

IBERIFIER — Iberian Digital Media Observatory

Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Report

Deliverable — D4.2

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1. Executive Summary

The report *Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal* provides key insights into the ways in which the Portuguese handle, assimilate and disseminate scientific information and disinformation in their daily lives. In this research we came across a diverse and complex range of perceptions, attitudes and behaviors that mixes institutionalised information flows with informal avenues of information made relevant by the way users perceive these sources in terms of their credibility.

In that sense, the key findings that follow must be read in the light of two overarching trends which are visible across the whole report: a) the consumption of scientific information has left the institutional communication channels and people access it in all sorts of ways and b) at this point the frequent exposure to disinformation is not an if but a matter of “when, how, where, who” as the channels used by legitimate scientific actors are the same used by those aiming to disinform – and in some ways, the latter are much more proficient in using those channels than the former. This raises significant challenges in terms of communication of scientific topics, in particular during crisis moments (eg. the pandemic, climate catastrophes, etc.)

The key findings for this report, by chapter, are as follows:

4. Science information consumption habits

Q1. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received information on any of the following topics via your social media, instant messaging apps or in conversations with other people?, 2026 (%)

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

- Information that relates to scientific topics is unevenly distributed across topics, with health-related domains occupying the most visible position in everyday information flows. Recent exposure is highest for wellness and nutrition and health and medicine, while environment and ecology is less salient, with technology in an intermediate position. This suggests that science-related information is more present when it is perceived as directly connected to everyday life, bodily well-being, or personal risk.
- Age and education structure exposure and access more strongly than gender or political orientation. Younger respondents report higher recent exposure across most scientific topics, especially wellness and science and technology, while older respondents display lower recent exposure. At the same time, higher education is associated with greater reported contact with scientific topics, particularly science and technology and health-related information.
- Active research into scientific topics relies primarily on accessible digital and informal sources. Social media, online video platforms, messaging apps and other easily accessible channels are more frequently used than institutional websites, scientific publications or technical books. This does not necessarily indicate distrust in formal sources, but rather that everyday information-seeking is shaped by convenience, accessibility and platform routines.
- Trust and usage do not fully overlap. Interpersonal sources and traditional media are trusted more than social media, messaging apps and online video platforms, even though the latter are frequently used. This reinforces a core tension in the science information ecosystem: citizens often encounter scientific content in environments they do not consider the most trustworthy.
- Communication habits are therefore stratified by both access and credibility. Younger groups rely more heavily on digital and social sources, while older and more educated groups show greater proximity to traditional and formal channels. As such, the broader context in which science disinformation circulates is an hybrid information environment where exposure, trust and active search do not follow the same hierarchy.

5. Credibility and the propagation of disinformation in scientific matters

- The experiment shows that respondents can distinguish between real and false scientific headlines, but only partially. Real headlines generally receive higher reliability scores, especially vaccine-related real headlines. However, some fake headlines, particularly the ones framed through familiar wellness or health optimisation narratives, are perceived as relatively credible. This suggests that science disinformation does not need to be overtly conspiratorial to appear plausible.
- Verification intention is high but ambiguous. Several false headlines produce high stated willingness to verify, such as claims about cortisol and weight loss or mercury in vaccines. This may signal doubt, but also topic salience in the public sphere, anxiety, curiosity or perceived relevance. Verification intention should therefore not

be interpreted simply as resistance to disinformation; it may also reflect uncertainty or higher engagement.

- Sharing intentions are consistently higher in personal circles than through social media and messaging platforms. Respondents are more willing to discuss or share both true and false headlines with family, friends or colleagues than through digital channels. This finding is central because it highlights interpersonal communication as a relevant pathway for the circulation of science-related information and disinformation, alongside platform-based dissemination.
- When respondents are targeted with accuracy-oriented nudges we find that these are more effective than emotion-oriented nudges in the presentation of news headlines. Prompts aiming to foster credibility checks and verification of news are more consistently associated with reduced sharing intention, particularly when compared with the control group. The combined nudge also tends to reduce sharing, but not always more than the credibility prompt alone. By contrast, the emotional nudge alone is less protective and, in some cases, appears to sustain or increase sharing intention.
- The experiment supports interventions that introduce credibility reflection at the point of sharing. The findings suggest that asking individuals to consider reliability and verification before sharing can reduce the circulation of scientific headlines, including false ones. However, the effect depends on the topic, headline, channel and emotional profile of the content and we find no evidence of a universal nudge effect.

6. Factors associated with perceived credibility and susceptibility to disinformation

- Conspiracy beliefs around scientific topics are present at moderate levels and vary strongly by education and political orientation. Agreement is highest for narratives involving institutional concealment, such as pharmaceutical companies hiding vaccine dangers or hidden cancer cures. More specific and widely debunked claims, such as the government hiding that vaccines causing autism, receive lower agreement. This suggests that broad suspicion of institutions may be more socially resonant than highly specific false claims.
- Education is a central protective factor across scientific literacy, media literacy and conspiracy belief. Higher education is associated with lower agreement with conspiracy narratives, higher ability to identify controlled comparison as the most scientific method to test a medicine, and stronger knowledge of the media ecosystem. The educational gradient is one of the most consistent patterns in the report.
- Scientific literacy is moderate rather than consolidated. Only 48% of respondents identify comparison between treated and untreated groups as the most scientific way to test a medicine. However, there are significant proportions of people selecting less rigorous alternatives or report uncertainty, indicating that basic scientific reasoning and knowledge of the scientific method at a basic level is unevenly distributed.

- Media literacy is fragmented. Respondents are more familiar with platform-related mechanisms, such as algorithmic personalisation, and with private ownership of media companies, but less knowledgeable about RTP’s funding model or the distinction between signed news texts and opinion pieces. This indicates that knowledge of digital platform logic may be stronger than knowledge of institutional and professional features of journalism, despite the fact that institutional sources are, by definition, more trusted as sources of information.
- News-finds-me attitudes are moderate and marked by ambivalence. Respondents do not strongly endorse passive news consumption, but neither do they clearly reject it. Younger respondents and those on the far-right show higher agreement with the idea that news can reach them without active seeking, especially through social media. This is relevant because passive reliance on platform and peer-mediated information flows may increase vulnerability to disinformation.

7. Perceptions on disinformation in day-to-day life

- Perceived exposure to disinformation is widespread but topic-dependent. Respondents most often report encountering potentially false information about nutrition and well-being and climate change, followed by medical treatments and alternative therapies. Vaccines and wildfires are less frequently identified, suggesting that perceived disinformation is shaped not only by actual circulation but also by topic salience and recognisability.
- Social media and video-based platforms are the dominant perceived gateways of suspected disinformation. Among those who believe they encountered false information, social media is the main reported channel, followed by online video platforms and messaging apps. Traditional media, television, radio and print / digital news are less frequently identified, although still relevant and playing a role in the perceived flows of disinformation.
- Self-reported sharing of suspected false information is limited but not negligible. Around one in eight respondents report having shared information they thought might be false, either through digital channels or face-to-face/telephone conversations. The prominence of interpersonal sharing reinforces the importance of private and semi-private circulation in disinformation dynamics.

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

- A third-person effect is clearly visible. Respondents express substantially more confidence in their own capacity to identify disinformation than in the ability of the average Portuguese person. This aligns with literature on perceived media effects and suggests that disinformation vulnerability is often externalised onto others but also affects the overall perception that people have of the quality of the democratic system.
- AI is perceived more as a risk amplifier than as a solution. Respondents agree more strongly that AI makes it easier, faster and cheaper to spread fake news than that it helps debunk rumours or lies. This dual but asymmetrical perception reflects a broader public ambivalence: AI is recognised as useful, but its corrective potential is less trusted than its disruptive power.

8. Attitudes on disinformation and science

Q17. [Press freedom] Please indicate which of these two statements you agree with most:, 2026 (%)

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

- There is broad consensus that disinformation has serious social consequences. Respondents strongly agree that disinformation can manipulate people's beliefs, generate distrust in institutions, harm public health and threaten democracy. The highest agreement concerns manipulation and institutional distrust, indicating that

citizens understand disinformation not only as an informational problem but as a systemic social risk.

- Respondents show willingness to accept regulatory trade-offs to combat disinformation. A clear majority prefer government measures to restrict false information online, even if this limits press freedom. This is one of the strongest normative findings in the report and suggests that concern about informational harm can outweigh abstract commitments to unrestricted press freedom.
- However, support for intervention is not uniform across demographics. Younger respondents, older respondents and ideological extremes show comparatively greater caution regarding restrictions on press freedom. This indicates that while regulatory willingness is broadly shared, it is also shaped by political and generational factors.
- Citizens identify disinformation as a multi-actor ecosystem. Influencers and online personalities are viewed as the greatest threat, ahead of many institutional actors. Lobbies, domestic political actors, social media platform owners and foreign political actors form a second tier. This reflects a public perception of disinformation as simultaneously platform-based, political, individualised and socially diffuse.
- The findings align with literature framing disinformation as an ecosystemic disorder. Respondents do not attribute responsibility to a single actor; instead, they recognise multiple sources and infrastructures of disinformation, with digital-native actors playing a particularly prominent role.

9. Trust

- Attitudes toward science and technology are broadly positive but not uncritical. Nearly half of respondents believe the benefits of science and technology outweigh the drawbacks, while a substantial minority see benefits and drawbacks as balanced. This indicates optimism moderated by caution or mistrust rather than unconditional techno-scientific enthusiasm.
- Education is strongly associated with more positive evaluations of science and technology. Highly educated respondents are much more likely to be techno-optimists, i.e., to see the benefits of technology outweighing its drawbacks and less likely to emphasise risks. By contrast, respondents with lower education and those at ideological extremes show more sceptical or ambivalent positions.
- Interpersonal trust is moderate and cautious. The overall mean is slightly below the midpoint of the scale, with respondents leaning toward the idea that one can never be too careful when dealing with others. Strong trust is rare, and the largest share of respondents choose the midpoint, suggesting ambivalence rather than either deep distrust or strong confidence.
- Trust in institutions follows a clear hierarchy. Scientists and IPMA¹ are the most trusted actors in relation to science, health and environmental issues, followed by international organisations such as the UN / WHO and the European Union.

¹ Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera, the Portuguese agency equivalent to AEMET.

Journalists and national political actors occupy lower trust positions, with politicians receiving the weakest evaluation.

- The trust landscape strengthens the central role of expertise in the consideration of the trustworthiness of sources. Scientific and technical actors retain credibility, but political institutions remain weakly trusted. This has implications for science communication and public policy: credible expertise may be available, but its translation into public policies depends on institutions that citizens trust less.

Q21. To what extent do you trust the following institutions or groups to tackle issues related to science and technology, health or the environment in a scale of 1 to 4 where 1-Nothing and 4-A lot, 2026 (means)

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1 to 4 where 1-Nothing and 4-A lot.

10. Scientific populism

- The relationship between science and society is marked by ambivalence. Respondents show some confidence in scientific knowledge, but also express suspicion toward scientists' independence, especially the idea that scientists may be aligned with politicians and businesses. This indicates that public scepticism is not necessarily anti-science in a simple sense, but often concerns the perceived institutional embedding of science.

- There is support for public involvement in science, but not a wholesale rejection of expertise. Respondents moderately endorse the idea that ordinary people should be involved in decisions about scientific topics and that lived experience should matter alongside scientific recommendations. At the same time, support for giving ordinary people a direct say in scientists' work is weaker, suggesting a differentiated view of participation.

Q22. *The following statements refer to the relationship between science and society. To what extent do you agree or disagree with them?, By Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)*

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale 1 to 7 where 1=Completely disagree and 7=Completely agree.

- Political orientation is the strongest marker of scientific populist attitudes. Far-right respondents show systematically higher agreement with sceptical and participatory claims about science, including the idea that scientists are entangled with political and economic interests. Far-left respondents show lower agreement with these anti-elitist framings. This points to a politicised critique of scientific authority.
- Respondents are generally willing to share scientific views, even in conflictual contexts. Willingness to express opinions on scientific issues is above the scale midpoint across all items and is particularly high among far-right respondents. This suggests that scientific debate in public life may be shaped not only by knowledge or trust, but also by communicative assertiveness and ideological identity.
- Egalitarian values are broadly endorsed, but ideological divisions persist. Respondents strongly support considering all groups and equality between groups as ideals, while rejecting explicit group domination. However, resistance to pushing for equality is more visible among far-right respondents, pointing to a tension between abstract support for equality and attitudes toward active equality-promoting measures.

2. Introduction

This report, titled *Social Perception of Scientific Disinformation in Portugal*, is part of the IBERIFIER working package devoted to strategy and policy research. Since the creation of IBERIFIER in 2021, the strategy and policy research working package has provided the framework for research on the multidimensional impacts of disinformation in terms of its causes and impacts at the social, political, economic, technological and cultural level, highlighted reports such as the one published by Badillo-Matos et al. (2023).

Despite the Iberian, dual country logic that pervades IBERIFIER scientific activities this report serves different purposes in Portugal and Spain. Whereas, in the Spanish case, the equivalent report published alongside this one aims to update a first document published in 2023 (FECYT et al., 2023), in the case of Portugal this is the first study of its kind to cover the topic of scientific disinformation in such an extensive way in the country.

With coordination by FECYT, in Spain, and lead by OberCom and Iscte in Portugal this research aims to fill a wide gap felt in the research in regards to the way the Iberians engage with scientific disinformation. Either due to its inherent complexity or to its central importance in the contemporary news agenda, scientific topics are among the most complex to study.

The overlap between science and politics has become particularly salient due to the COVID pandemic and to climate change and environmental catastrophes. The relationship between publics and science information has much more sensitive to impacts that go beyond the ones covered and measured in the field of media studies. For this reason, we gauge a wide diversity of concepts to map a perceptual, attitudinal and behavioral framework that ranges from day-to-day activities to more abstract and subjective consideration in the way people perceive science and related disinformation.

To accomplish this, the following research objectives were designed:

1. Update the indicators from the first edition and identify any changes in habits, perceptions and attitudes since 2022 in Spain / Expand the research on the topic to Portugal.
2. Analyse the perception of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a vehicle for disinformation and as a verification tool.
3. Examine the attitudes of the Iberian public towards scientists and institutional science.
4. Explore conspiracy theories in the scientific sphere and their relationship with susceptibility to disinformation.
5. Estimate the causal effect of truthfulness information and emotional arousal on the intention to share true and false scientific news.

The report is structured as follows: an initial methodological chapter in which the procedures are described precedes 8 thematic chapters - science information consumption habits; credibility and disinformation in scientific matters; factors associated with perceived credibility and susceptibility to disinformation; perceptions of disinformation in day-to-day life; attitudes on disinformation and science; trust and scientific populism. All chapters include descriptive analysis of variables as well as crossings with gender, age, education and political orientation with the exception of chapter 5 (credibility and disinformation in scientific matters) which relates to an experiment in which we test the effects of different nudges in the sharing of scientific real and fake news (see Methodology up next for further description). Two final chapters describe the habits of access to internet as well as the demographic variables. The most relevant findings of the report are highlighted in the executive summary at the beginning of this report.

3. Methodology

The questionnaire for the *Social Perception of Science Disinformation in Science in Portugal* was conducted by YouGov between March 2nd and March 19th 2026 covering individuals aged between 16 and 74, in a total of 2031 interviews, 1930 in CAWI (Web) and 101 in CATI (telephone) (95,1% and 4,9% of the total, respectively). CATI interviews focused on the 55 to 74 years of age demographic to ensure representation of older, non-internet users. Quotas were applied for gender, age and education as well as region.

The questionnaire was split into 7 blocks of questions plus one block which contains the experiment on the credibility and propagation of disinformation in scientific matters applied only to the web sample. The experiment, which is analysed and described in depth in chapter 5, is a cross-subject experiment designed to estimate the causal effect of two types of cognitive intervention (nudge) on the intention to share news according to headlines.

The intervention consist of asking the respondents of three different groups, before answering the question on sharing intention (Q6.4), to reflect on (a) the emotional reaction the news elicits in them (Q6.1), (b) the credibility of the information and their intention to verify it (Q6.2 and Q6.3), or both. Respondents on a fourth group, proceeded directly to the sharing question without any prior intervention for control purposes.

The experiment was run across groups in the following way:

Group	Denominación	Questions presented	Description and purpose
1 (n=424)	<i>Combined nudge</i>	Q6.1. P6.2 + P6.3 + P6.4	Emotional reflection and credibility assessment prior to the question.
2 (n=456)	<i>Emotional nudge</i>	P6.1 + P6.4	Just emotional reflection before the dissemination
3 (n=450)	<i>Trustworthiness nudge</i>	P6.2 + P6.3 + P6.4	Just credibility assessment and verification before the question.
4 (n=464)	<i>Control</i>	P6.4	No nudge at all, just the question.
99 (n=236)	<i>Excluded from experiment (CATI)</i>	–	Interview by phone, did not participate in the experiment

Note: Questions are as follows: Q6.1. How does this headline make you feel? (options are: helpless, anxious, optimistic, angry, guilty, ashamed, depressed, pessimistic, indifferent, empathetic); Q6.2. How reliable do consider this information to be? (reply in scale of 1 to 7 where 1=Not reliable at all and 7=completely reliable); Q6.3. If you came across this headline online would check its truthfulness? (Yes / No); Q6.4. How likely would it be for you to share this headline / news with people in personal circle / on social media and messaging apps (reply in scale if 1 to 7 where 1=Would not share at all and 7=Would definitely share).

Each questionnaire presented eight randomly selected headlines: one false and one true for each of the four topics (climate, diet and health, vaccines, and artificial intelligence). For

each combination of topic and truthfulness, there were two headline variants, assigned at random with an approximate 50% probability and distributed evenly across the experimental groups.

The possible headlines were selected among the ones presented in the following list:

Real	
Topic	Headline
<i>Climate</i>	Climate change is linked to the severity of the extreme wildfires that occurred in Portugal in 2025. (n=877)
	Biofuels are not 100% renewable. (n=919)
<i>Health / nutrition</i>	Using sun cream in real life does not cause a vitamin D deficiency. (n=897)
	Homeopathy does not work (beyond the placebo effect). (n=898)
<i>Vaccines</i>	The flu virus adapts and changes from season to season, so you need to have the vaccine every year. (n=866)
	The vaccine against human papillomavirus is effective and safe. (n=930)
<i>AI</i>	An AI's responses may show a flattery bias (agreeing with everything we say). (n=881)
	An AI model is like a parrot: it can repeat conversations, but it doesn't understand what it's saying. (n=915)
Fake	
Topic	Headline
<i>Climate</i>	Some countries spray clouds before they reach the peninsula to disperse the rain. (n=921)
	The recent floods are the result of a HAARP weather attack. (n=874)
<i>Health / nutrition</i>	There are foods that help reduce cortisol and thus aid weight loss. (n=911)
	A possible link has been found between autism and the consumption of paracetamol during pregnancy. (n=884)
<i>Vaccines</i>	The mercury in vaccines is harmful to health. (n=943)
	COVID-19 vaccines cause infertility and can lead to male sexual impotence. (n=853)
<i>AI</i>	AI can provide therapy on a par with any qualified psychologist. (n=913)
	Current AI has been designed to wipe out humanity. (n=882)

4. Science information consumption habits

In this first chapter we analyse the relationship between the Portuguese and science information, focusing on the access in the recent past, the frequency of the access and the gateways in which citizens engage with this kind of information. This initial characterisation of the science information habits lays the basis for subsequent analysis by providing a detailed understanding of how people engage with scientific information in their day-to-day life. The focus is on information relating to environment and ecology, health and medicine, wellness and nutrition and science and technology.

4.1. Recent acquisition of information on scientific topics

Q1. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received information on any of the following topics via your social media, instant messaging apps or in conversations with other people?, 2026 (%)

	Environment and ecology	Health and medicine	Wellness and nutrition	Science and technology
Yes	37,6%	56,3%	57,2%	45,9%
No	61,8%	43,6%	42,2%	53,5%
Don't know	0,4%	0,1%	0,5%	0,4%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,1%	0,1%	0,2%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Exposure to information on scientific topics in the previous seven days varies significantly across thematic areas. Health and medicine (56,3%) and wellness and nutrition (57,2%) emerge as the domains with the highest levels of reported exposure, followed by science and technology (45,9%).

In contrast, environment and ecology stands out as the least salient topic, with only 37,6% of respondents reporting recent contact with related information. There is a differentiated visibility of scientific domains in everyday information flows, with health-related topics occupying a more prominent position, compared to wider fields which are not, at first hand, directly related with the individual and his or her well-being.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Q1. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received information on any of the following topics via your social media, instant messaging apps or in conversations with other people? By Gender and Age, 2026 (%)

	All	Men	Women	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Environment and ecology									
Yes	37,6%	38,6%	36%	49,0%	37,2%	41,2%	39,4%	37,1%	26,9%
No	61,8%	60,9%	63%	51,0%	62,2%	58,8%	59,8%	62,2%	71,8%
Don't know	0,4%	0,3%	1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,6%	0,7%	0,9%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,2%	0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
Health and medicine									
Yes	56,3%	54,4%	58,0%	60,0%	58,5%	56,3%	60,6%	59,7%	40,5%
No	43,6%	45,3%	41,9%	40,0%	41,2%	43,7%	39,1%	40,3%	59,2%
Don't know	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%
Wellness and nutrition									
Yes	57,2%	51,3%	62,8%	69,5%	63,2%	57,6%	59,3%	61,4%	35,8%
No	42,2%	48,1%	36,6%	30,5%	36,2%	42,1%	39,9%	38,1%	63,0%
Don't know	0,5%	0,5%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,6%	0,5%	1,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,6%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
Science and technology									
Yes	45,9%	51,0%	41,0%	56,0%	52,0%	48,0%	51,0%	46,0%	24,0%
No	53,5%	48,0%	59,0%	44,0%	47,0%	52,0%	48,0%	54,0%	75,0%
Don't know	0,4%	0,0%	1,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,0%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Gender differences are generally modest but reveal some noteworthy patterns. Women report higher exposure to health and medicine (58,0% vs. 54,4%) and especially to wellness and nutrition (62,8% vs. 51,3%), while men show higher exposure to science and technology (51,0% vs. 41,0%) but only slightly to environment-related content (38,6% vs. 36,0%). These differences point to a gendered distribution of informational interests or algorithmic exposure, as well as their perception of technology, particularly when it comes to lifestyle and health-related topics.

Age emerges as a highly structuring variable. Younger respondents (17–24) consistently report the highest levels of exposure across most topics, particularly in wellness and nutrition (69,5%) and science and technology (56,0%). Older groups, especially those aged 65+ show substantial lower exposure, with only 26,9% reporting contact with environmental information and 24,0% with science and technology content. This pattern suggests a strong generational divide in the circulation and consumption of scientific information, potentially reflecting differences in media use and digital engagement.

Q1. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received information on any of the following topics via your social media, instant messaging apps or in conversations with other people? By Education, 2026 (%)

	All	Low Education	Medium Education	High Education
Environment and ecology				
Yes	37,6%	31,3%	40,4%	40,5%
No	61,8%	67,7%	58,9%	59,2%
Don't know	0,4%	0,6%	0,4%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,3%	0,3%	0,0%
Health and medicine				
Yes	56,3%	47,7%	58,1%	62,5%
No	43,6%	52,0%	41,6%	37,5%
Don't know	0,1%	0,2%	0,1%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,1%	0,0%
Wellness and nutrition				
Yes	57,2%	43,1%	60,0%	67,6%
No	42,2%	55,8%	39,3%	32,2%
Don't know	0,5%	0,9%	0,4%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,3%	0,0%
Science and technology				
Yes	45,9%	33,0%	47,0%	57,0%
No	53,5%	66,0%	52,0%	43,0%
Don't know	0,4%	1,0%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Low Education=up to 9th grade (2º/3º Ciclo), Medium Education=Secondary Education / Professional degree (Secundário / Curso Técnico Superior Profissional), High Education=Any academic degree.

Educational attainment is also strongly associated with exposure levels. Individuals with higher education consistently report greater contact with all scientific topics, particularly health and medicine (62,5%), wellness and nutrition (67,6%), and science and technology (57,0%). Conversely, respondents with lower levels of education display substantially lower exposure, especially in science and technology (33,0%) and wellness-related content (43,1%). This gradient reinforces the role of education as a key factor in access to and engagement with scientific information.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Q1. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received information on any of the following topics via your social media, instant messaging apps or in conversations with other people? By Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	All	1 – Far-left	2	3	4	5	6	7 – Far-right
Environment and ecology								
Yes	37,6%	43,8%	46,4%	33,4%	35,6%	40,8%	42,6%	37,0%
No	61,8%	53,1%	50,0%	66,3%	63,9%	58,7%	57,4%	61,6%
Don't know	0,4%	3,1%	2,4%	0,3%	0,5%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,0%	1,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	1,4%
Health and medicine								
Yes	56,3%	50,0%	54,2%	51,2%	54,7%	59,0%	65,3%	61,6%
No	43,6%	46,9%	44,6%	48,8%	45,2%	41,0%	34,7%	38,4%
Don't know	0,1%	3,1%	1,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
Wellness and nutrition								
Yes	57,2%	50,0%	50,0%	53,9%	56,0%	58,5%	68,7%	58,9%
No	42,2%	46,9%	46,4%	45,8%	43,7%	40,7%	31,3%	39,7%
Don't know	0,5%	3,1%	2,4%	0,3%	0,4%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	1,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
Science and technology								
Yes	45,9%	34,4%	50,6%	45,0%	42,0%	54,0%	50,3%	43,1%
No	53,5%	62,5%	47,0%	54,7%	57,4%	45,5%	49,7%	55,6%
Don't know	0,4%	3,1%	2,4%	0,3%	0,5%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	1,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Finally, political orientation reveals more nuanced patterns. While exposure to environment-related information is relatively balanced across the ideological spectrum, health and medicine, as well as wellness and nutrition, tend to show higher levels of exposure among respondents positioned towards the centre-right (positions 5–7), peaking at 65,3% and 68,7%, respectively.

Science and technology exposure is more uneven, with lower levels at the political extremes, particularly on the far-left (34,4%). These variations suggest that while scientific information circulates broadly across political groups, it is reasonable to assume that certain domains may be more salient within specific ideological segments.

Q2. Generally speaking, how often do you get information about..., 2026 (% and Means)

	%					
	Economy and business	Environment and ecology	Politics	Health and medicine	Wellness and nutrition	Science and technology
1- Every day or almost every day	16,7%	10,0%	30,8%	17,0%	19,9%	14,8%
2 - At least once a week	24,3%	25,9%	21,9%	31,5%	30,4%	27,2%
3 - Several times a month	24,9%	33,3%	20,5%	35,4%	31,3%	30,0%
4 - Hardly ever or never	33,8%	30,6%	26,6%	15,9%	18,4%	27,8%
I don't know	0,2%	0,2%	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,2%
I'd rather not say	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
	Means					
	2,76	2,85	2,43	2,50	2,48	2,71

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale 1 to 4 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 4=Hardly ever or never.

The frequency with which respondents report accessing information on different topics reveals important variations across domains. Overall, politics stands out as the most frequently accessed topic, with 30,8% of respondents reporting exposure on a daily or almost daily basis and the lowest mean value (2,43) on the scale (inverted scale, where lower values indicate higher frequency).

Health and medicine (2,50) and wellness and nutrition (2,48) also show relatively high levels of regular exposure, with a majority of respondents indicating access at least once a week or several times a month. In contrast, environment and ecology (2,85) and economy and business (2,76) display lower levels of frequent engagement, with higher proportions reporting access only several times a month or hardly ever. Science and technology occupies an intermediate position (2,71), with a relatively balanced distribution across frequency categories.

Considering demographic differences (see table in next page) gender differences reveal a consistent pattern across topics. Women tend to report lower frequent exposure (lower mean values) to economy and business (2,99 vs. 2,51 for men), politics (2,61 vs. 2,23), and science and technology (2,92 vs. 2,49), while men report slightly higher frequency in politics (2,23 vs 2,61) and science and technology (2,49 vs. 2,92). These differences suggest a gendered difference for information consumption, although the scale of variation remains moderate.

Age differences are particularly pronounced and appear to suggest a life-cycle effect. Younger respondents (17–24) consistently report higher frequency of exposure across most topics (e.g., 2,47 in economy and business, 2,41 in health and medicine), whereas the oldest group (65+) reports substantially lower frequency (higher numerical values on the scale), especially in economy and business (3,18), environment and ecology (3,21), and science and technology (3,24). This suggests that older individuals engage less regularly with informational content across domains, while younger cohorts display more frequent patterns of exposure.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Q2. Generally speaking, how often do you get information about..., By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Economy and business	Environment and ecology	Politics	Health and medicine	Wellness and nutrition	Science and technology
All	2,76	2,85	2,43	2,50	2,48	2,71
Male	2,51	2,82	2,23	2,55	2,57	2,49
Female	2,99	2,88	2,61	2,46	2,39	2,92
17-24	2,47	2,69	2,33	2,41	2,34	2,41
25-34	2,67	2,82	2,46	2,49	2,39	2,58
35-44	2,71	2,77	2,5	2,45	2,44	2,6
45-54	2,75	2,8	2,42	2,47	2,48	2,66
55-64	2,68	2,77	2,22	2,39	2,38	2,67
65+	3,18	3,21	2,67	2,81	2,82	3,24
Low education	3,12	3,04	2,77	2,68	2,76	3,03
Medium education	2,77	2,82	2,43	2,48	2,42	2,7
High education	2,41	2,69	2,11	2,35	2,29	2,41
1 - Far-Left	3,05	2,85	2,83	2,67	2,8	3,00
2	3,11	2,88	2,36	2,78	2,8	2,86
3	2,86	2,88	2,4	2,59	2,51	2,76
4 - Center	2,85	2,86	2,58	2,47	2,47	2,76
5	2,49	2,77	2,18	2,45	2,41	2,55
6	2,5	2,9	2,28	2,5	2,44	2,65
7 - Far-Right	2,62	2,75	2,23	2,31	2,44	2,57

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 4 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 4=Hardly ever or never; b) Low Education=up to 9th grade (2º/3º Ciclo), Medium Education=Secondary Education / Professional degree (Secundário / Curso Técnico Superior Profissional), High Education=Any academic degree.

Educational attainment is also strongly associated with frequency of information access. Respondents with lower levels of education report more less exposure across all topics, whereas those with higher education display more!! frequent engagement. This inverse relationship may reflect differences in media routines or the selectivity of information consumption, with more educated individuals engaging more frequently with general informational content.

Political orientation reveals differentiated patterns across topics. Respondents positioned on the far-left report relatively lower frequency of exposure across most domains, particularly economy and business (3,05), politics (2,83), and science and technology (3,00). A similar pattern is observed among respondents at position 2. In contrast, individuals located towards the centre-right and right (positions 5–7) tend to report more frequent exposure, especially in politics and economy-related topics. However, variation across the

ideological spectrum is less pronounced than for age and education, suggesting that political orientation plays a secondary role compared to structural socio-demographic factors. Across Portuguese society, placement on the political spectrum does not determine information usage patterns but having a political orientation is key, the proportion of politically non-oriented / undecided Portuguese voters who claim to never avoid the news is of 12,0%, compared to 30% of those on the left, 27% on the centre and 25% on the right (Cardoso et al., 2025).

4.2. Frequency of active research into scientific topics

Q3. How often do you use each of the following sources to find out about..., 2026 (Means)

	Environment and ecology	Health and medicine	Wellness and nutrition	Science and technology
Social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok...), blogs or forums	3,47	3,21	3,1	2,81
Online video platforms (YouTube, Twitch,,)	3,81	3,61	3,55	3,22
Conversations on messaging apps (WhatsApp, Telegram, Line)	3,78	3,53	3,51	3,19
Television and online TV platforms (Netflix, HBO Max, Prime Video, Disney+, Apple TV, Sky, Filmin, etc.)	3,62	3,43	3,45	3,04
Online or print daily newspapers	3,93	3,81	3,85	3,49
Popular science or technical books or magazines; online encyclopaedias (e.g, Wikipedia)	4,05	3,91	3,9	3,87
Radio and/or podcasts	3,87	3,69	3,71	3,4
Scientific publications or journals	4,12	3,99	4	3,99
Other print and/or online magazines	4,11	3,97	3,95	3,92
Institutional websites (Ministries, universities, WHO...)	4,07	3,89	4,01	3,94
Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT, Google summaries, Gemini...)	3,9	3,56	3,6	3,35

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 5=Almost never or never.

The analysis of sources used to actively search for information on scientific topics reveals a clear hierarchy in the informational ecosystem, structured primarily by levels of accessibility and formality. Overall, more informal and easily accessible sources—such as social media, online video platforms, and messaging applications—are used more frequently (i.e., lower

mean values), particularly in the domains of science and technology (2,81 for social media) and health-related topics. In contrast, more formal and specialised sources such as scientific publications, institutional websites, and technical books are used considerably less frequently across all domains, consistently displaying the highest mean values (around 4,0 or above on an inverted scale, where higher values represent lower frequency of use).

Across thematic areas, science and technology stands out as the domain where most sources are used more frequently, suggesting a broader diversification of entry points into this topic. Conversely, environment and ecology tends to show higher mean values across most sources, indicating less frequent active search behaviour. Health and medicine and wellness and nutrition occupy intermediate positions, combining relatively frequent use of digital and interpersonal sources with more occasional consultation of formal information channels.

Gender differences are present but relatively moderate (see Table in next page). Women tend to use formal and semi-formal sources more frequently than men, including online newspapers, encyclopaedias, institutional websites, and scientific publications, across most thematic areas. Men, on the other hand, report slightly more frequent use of social media and video platforms in some domains, particularly environment and science and technology. These differences suggest a somewhat more diversified and formalised information-seeking pattern among women.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Q3. How often do you use each of the following sources to find out about..., By Gender, 2026 (Means)

	All	Men	Women
Environment and ecology			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,47	3,24	2,96
Online video platforms	3,81	3,44	3,66
Conversations on messaging apps	3,78	3,48	3,54
Television and online TV platforms	3,62	3,41	3,5
Online or print daily newspapers	3,93	3,73	3,97
Popular science or technical books or magazines; online encyclopaedias	4,05	3,78	4,02
Radio and/or podcasts	3,87	3,65	3,77
Scientific publications or journals	4,12	3,88	4,13
Other print and/or online magazines	4,11	3,84	4,05
Institutional websites	4,07	3,94	4,07
Artificial Intelligence	3,9	3,59	3,61
Health and medicine			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,21	3,32	3,11
Online video platforms	3,61	3,45	3,76
Conversations on messaging apps	3,53	3,46	3,6
Television and online TV platforms	3,43	3,38	3,48
Online or print daily newspapers	3,81	3,68	3,93
Popular science or technical books or magazines; online encyclopaedias	3,91	3,77	4,04
Radio and/or podcasts	3,69	3,57	3,8
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	3,85	4,12
Other print and/or online magazines	3,97	3,82	4,13
Institutional websites	3,89	3,8	3,97
Artificial Intelligence	3,56	3,55	3,57
Wellness and nutrition			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,1	3,47	3,47
Online video platforms	3,55	3,6	4,02
Conversations on messaging apps	3,51	3,64	3,93
Television and online TV platforms	3,45	3,5	3,74
Online or print daily newspapers	3,85	3,77	4,09
Popular science or technical books or magazines; online encyclopaedias	3,9	3,87	4,24
Radio and/or podcasts	3,71	3,71	4,02
Scientific publications or journals	4	3,94	4,3
Other print and/or online magazines	3,95	3,94	4,27
Institutional websites	4,01	3,92	4,21
Artificial Intelligence	3,6	3,8	3,99
Science and technology			
Social media, blogs or forums	2,81	2,76	2,88
Online video platforms	3,22	2,94	3,48
Conversations on messaging apps	3,19	3,08	3,31
Television and online TV platforms	3,04	2,9	3,16
Online or print daily newspapers	3,49	3,26	3,72
Popular science or technical books or magazines; online encyclopaedias	3,87	3,7	4,04
Radio and/or podcasts	3,40	3,23	3,56
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	3,81	4,16
Other print and/or online magazines	3,92	3,73	4,11
Institutional websites	3,94	3,81	4,08
Artificial Intelligence	3,35	3,24	3,47

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 5=Almost never or never; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q3 general table.

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Q3. How often do you use each of the following sources to find out about..., By Age, 2026
(Means)

	All	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Environment and ecology							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,47	2,76	2,84	2,99	3,16	2,97	3,68
Online video platforms	3,81	3,26	3,29	3,49	3,57	3,47	4,07
Conversations on messaging apps	3,78	3,25	3,41	3,53	3,68	3,28	3,73
Television and online TV platforms	3,62	3,35	3,53	3,57	3,56	3,26	3,38
Online or print daily newspapers	3,93	3,76	3,78	3,9	3,89	3,79	3,94
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	4,05	3,74	3,72	3,93	3,94	3,77	4,24
Radio and/or podcasts	3,87	3,59	3,77	3,71	3,73	3,64	3,76
Scientific publications or journals	4,12	3,78	3,8	3,97	4,06	3,95	4,32
Other print and/or online magazines	4,11	3,82	3,86	3,97	3,97	3,9	4,08
Institutional websites	4,07	3,61	3,8	3,96	3,95	4,08	4,44
Artificial Intelligence	3,97	3,12	3,3	3,47	3,62	3,58	4,25
Health and medicine							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,21	3,06	2,96	3,23	3,17	3,09	3,76
Online video platforms	3,61	3,33	3,42	3,59	3,58	3,49	4,12
Conversations on messaging apps	3,53	3,3	3,49	3,63	3,63	3,32	3,68
Television and online TV platforms	3,43	3,37	3,48	3,45	3,49	3,29	3,48
Online or print daily newspapers	3,81	3,81	3,73	3,85	3,8	3,68	4,05
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,91	3,72	3,68	3,87	3,98	3,82	4,24
Radio and/or podcasts	3,69	3,68	3,68	3,74	3,65	3,63	3,8
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	3,7	3,79	3,97	4,07	3,95	4,23
Other print and/or online magazines	3,97	3,85	3,79	4,03	3,97	3,92	4,22
Institutional websites	3,89	3,51	3,65	3,87	3,85	3,98	4,26
Artificial Intelligence	3,56	3,11	3,24	3,42	3,55	3,57	4,22
Wellness and nutrition							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,15	3,11	3,27	3,41	3,48	3,39	3,96
Online video platforms	3,55	3,53	3,67	3,83	3,79	3,7	4,25
Conversations on messaging apps	3,51	3,57	3,62	3,81	3,88	3,59	4,09
Television and online TV platforms	3,45	3,47	3,67	3,7	3,65	3,46	3,7
Online or print daily newspapers	3,85	3,79	3,82	3,94	3,98	3,86	4,09
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,95	3,85	3,77	4,04	4,06	4,11	4,37
Radio and/or podcasts	3,71	3,82	3,84	3,87	3,82	3,73	4,17
Scientific publications or journals	4	3,75	3,91	4,11	4,12	4,19	4,44
Other print and/or online magazines	3,95	3,87	3,98	4,14	4,1	4,05	4,39

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Institutional websites	4,0 1	3,61	3,86	4,06	4,05	4,13	4,44
Artificial Intelligence	3,6	3,47	3,66	3,81	3,91	3,92	4,36
Science and technology							
Social media, blogs or forums	2,8 1	2,48	2,59	2,55	2,68	2,8	3,71
Online video platforms	3,2 2	2,87	2,87	3,03	3,12	3,24	4,05
Conversations on messaging apps	3,1 9	3,02	3,11	3,05	3,06	3,06	3,85
Television and online TV platforms	3,0 4	2,99	3,13	2,92	2,87	2,89	3,55
Online or print daily newspapers	3,4 9	3,48	3,45	3,5	3,42	3,34	3,87
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,8 7	3,66	3,63	3,92	3,84	3,81	4,3
Radio and/or podcasts	3,4	3,38	3,42	3,22	3,22	3,3	3,97
Scientific publications or journals	3,9 9	3,56	3,76	3,97	4,04	3,99	4,35
Other print and/or online magazines	3,9 2	3,82	3,84	3,89	3,94	3,84	4,16
Institutional websites	3,9 4	3,32	3,74	3,87	3,9	4,02	4,5
Artificial Intelligence	3,3 5	2,83	3,03	3,08	3,31	3,44	4,18

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 5=Almost never or never; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q3 general table

Age (table in previous page) constitutes one of the most significant factors of differentiation. Younger respondents (17–24) rely more heavily on digital and social sources, including social media, video platforms, and messaging applications, while older groups, especially those above the 55 years old threshold, show markedly higher mean values (i.e., lower frequency) for these channels. Conversely, older respondents demonstrate relatively greater engagement with traditional and formal sources, such as newspapers, radio, institutional websites, and scientific publications. This indicates a generational divide not only in frequency but also in the type of sources used for active information seeking.

Educational attainment (table in the next page) further reinforces this structuring. Individuals with higher levels of education tend to use more formal and specialised sources more frequently, including scientific publications, institutional websites, and encyclopaedic resources, while those with lower levels of education rely comparatively more on accessible and mediated channels such as television, social media, and messaging platforms. This gradient highlights the role of education in shaping both the depth and the nature of information-seeking practices.

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Q3. How often do you use each of the following sources to find out about..., By Education, 2026 (Means)

	All	Low education	Medium education	High education
Environment and ecology				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,47	3,38	3,01	2,92
Online video platforms	3,81	3,7	3,47	3,5
Conversations on messaging apps	3,78	3,63	3,46	3,46
Television and online TV platforms	3,62	3,36	3,45	3,55
Online or print daily newspapers	3,93	3,96	3,84	3,75
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	4,05	4,08	3,85	3,79
Radio and/or podcasts	3,87	3,71	3,72	3,7
Scientific publications or journals	4,12	4,16	3,92	3,94
Other print and/or online magazines	4,11	4,02	3,96	3,86
Institutional websites	4,07	4,22	3,97	3,83
Artificial Intelligence	3,9	3,91	3,52	3,38
Health and medicine				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,21	3,39	3,12	3,15
Online video platforms	3,61	3,75	3,53	3,55
Conversations on messaging apps	3,53	3,61	3,48	3,51
Television and online TV platforms	3,43	3,3	3,47	3,53
Online or print daily newspapers	3,81	3,89	3,84	3,7
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,91	4,16	3,9	3,69
Radio and/or podcasts	3,69	3,68	3,72	3,67
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	4,19	3,92	3,86
Other print and/or online magazines	3,97	4,1	3,97	3,85
Institutional websites	3,89	4,17	3,84	3,67
Artificial Intelligence	3,56	3,88	3,47	3,34
Wellness and nutrition				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,1	3,61	3,39	3,4
Online video platforms	3,55	3,9	3,76	3,78
Conversations on messaging apps	3,51	3,81	3,73	3,82
Television and online TV platforms	3,45	3,57	3,61	3,68
Online or print daily newspapers	3,85	4	3,96	3,81
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,9	4,23	3,99	3,95
Radio and/or podcasts	3,71	3,92	3,87	3,81
Scientific publications or journals	4	4,26	4,1	4
Other print and/or online magazines	3,95	4,23	4,08	4
Institutional websites	4,01	4,23	4,03	3,94
Artificial Intelligence	3,6	4,07	3,86	3,78
Science and technology				
Social media, blogs or forums	2,81	3,12	2,68	2,67
Online video platforms	3,22	3,43	3,11	3,12
Conversations on messaging apps	3,19	3,42	3,02	3,15
Television and online TV platforms	3,04	3,12	2,95	3,05
Online or print daily newspapers	3,49	3,74	3,44	3,31
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,87	4,2	3,84	3,6
Radio and/or podcasts	3,4	3,58	3,35	3,27
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	4,24	3,96	3,78
Other print and/or online magazines	3,92	4,02	3,93	3,82
Institutional websites	3,94	4,27	3,94	3,64
Artificial Intelligence	3,35	3,73	3,23	3,12

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 5=Almost never or never; b) Low Education=up to 9th grade (2º/3º Ciclo), Medium Education=Secondary Education / Professional degree (Secundário / Curso Técnico Superior Profissional), High Education=Any academic degree; c) For complete description of categories with examples see Q3 general table.

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Q3. How often do you use each of the following sources to find out about..., By Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	All	1 – Far-left	2	3	4 – Center	5	6	7 – Far-right
Environment and ecology								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,47	2,85	3,46	3,28	3,14	2,91	2,96	2,71
Online video platforms	3,81	3,00	3,81	3,74	3,59	3,44	3,41	2,95
Conversations on messaging apps	3,78	3,25	3,88	3,66	3,58	3,34	3,45	2,92
Television and online TV platforms	3,62	3,48	3,53	3,48	3,48	3,44	3,4	3,22
Online or print daily newspapers	3,93	3,77	3,96	3,89	3,89	3,74	3,87	3,58
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	4,05	3,88	4,14	3,93	3,96	3,83	3,73	3,6
Radio and/or podcasts	3,87	3,37	3,81	3,7	3,74	3,64	3,77	3,48
Scientific publications or journals	4,12	3,82	4,21	4,07	4,05	3,94	3,97	3,58
Other print and/or online magazines	4,11	4,02	4,14	3,95	3,97	3,88	3,99	3,71
Institutional websites	4,07	3,93	4,16	4,12	4,06	3,9	3,8	3,75
Artificial Intelligence	3,9	3,74	3,95	3,82	3,62	3,43	3,44	2,97
Health and medicine								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,21	2,86	3,67	3,47	3,23	3,07	2,95	2,75
Online video platforms	3,61	2,74	3,88	3,87	3,63	3,54	3,28	3,12
Conversations on messaging apps	3,53	3,12	3,84	3,71	3,56	3,44	3,34	2,96
Television and online TV platforms	3,43	3,12	3,69	3,46	3,48	3,42	3,23	3,26
Online or print daily newspapers	3,81	3,67	4	3,88	3,86	3,71	3,7	3,64
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,91	3,95	4,05	3,89	4	3,83	3,67	3,68
Radio and/or podcasts	3,69	3,35	3,89	3,74	3,69	3,69	3,56	3,44
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	4,07	4,2	4,05	4,03	3,88	3,89	3,8
Other print and/or online magazines	3,97	3,75	4,23	4,06	3,99	3,94	3,78	3,78
Institutional websites	3,89	3,93	3,99	3,98	3,9	3,77	3,8	3,76
Artificial Intelligence	3,56	3,65	3,98	3,81	3,55	3,44	3,25	3,22
Wellness and nutrition								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,1	3,00	3,64	3,6	3,53	3,33	3,38	3,23
Online video platforms	3,55	3,03	3,99	3,92	3,84	3,8	3,64	3,46
Conversations on messaging apps	3,51	3,33	4,15	3,93	3,81	3,7	3,64	3,29
Television and online TV platforms	3,45	3,58	3,76	3,71	3,68	3,54	3,53	3,28
Online or print daily newspapers	3,85	3,73	3,91	3,97	3,99	3,84	3,94	3,59
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,9	3,96	4,13	4,13	4,13	3,93	3,97	3,69
Radio and/or podcasts	3,71	3,32	4,06	3,89	3,87	3,89	3,81	3,64
Scientific publications or journals	4	4,02	4,22	4,19	4,2	4,02	3,99	3,71
Other print and/or online magazines	3,95	3,96	4,27	4,16	4,13	4,02	4,14	3,7
Institutional websites	4,01	3,95	4,11	4,2	4,14	3,92	3,89	3,83
Artificial Intelligence	3,6	3,82	4,16	4,14	3,88	3,81	3,69	3,54
Science and technology								
Social media, blogs or forums	2,81	2,68	3,35	3,15	2,78	2,63	2,7	2,36
Online video platforms	3,22	2,88	3,43	3,48	3,23	3,11	2,97	2,71
Conversations on messaging apps	3,19	2,96	3,67	3,49	3,14	3,09	2,98	2,78
Television and online TV platforms	3,04	3,27	3,38	3,17	3,02	3,03	2,76	2,72
Online or print daily newspapers	3,49	3,52	3,71	3,54	3,56	3,27	3,63	3,36
Popular science; online encyclopaedias	3,87	3,74	4,05	3,88	3,96	3,74	3,77	3,65
Radio and/or podcasts	3,4	3,22	3,76	3,45	3,41	3,32	3,26	3,11
Scientific publications or journals	3,99	3,98	4,18	4,04	4,08	3,85	3,82	3,71
Other print and/or online magazines	3,92	3,93	4,07	3,95	3,95	3,81	3,96	3,87
Institutional websites	3,94	4,31	4,11	4,02	4	3,79	3,76	3,86
Artificial Intelligence	3,35	3,73	3,73	3,66	3,37	3,15	3,06	2,72

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=Every day or almost every day and 5=Almost never or never; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q3 general table.

Finally, political orientation (table in previous page) introduces more nuanced variations. Respondents positioned towards the left of the ideological spectrum generally report more frequent use of a wider range of sources, particularly formal and institutional ones, whereas those on the right tend to show lower frequency levels across several source types, especially in domains such as science and technology and environment. However, these differences are less pronounced than those observed for age and education, suggesting that political orientation plays a secondary role in structuring information-seeking behaviour.

In sum, the findings point to a stratified information ecosystem in which active research into scientific topics is predominantly mediated by accessible digital platforms, while more formal sources remain comparatively marginal. This structure is strongly shaped by age and education, with additional but more limited differentiation by gender and political orientation.

4.3. Communication channels

Q4. To what extent do you trust each of the following communication channels when seeking information on [TOPIC] (1 – I don't trust the source at all and 7 – I trust the source completely), 2026 (Means)

	Environment and ecology	Health and medicine	Wellness and nutrition	Science and technology
Social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok...), blogs or forums	3,70	3,61	3,78	3,71
Online video platforms (YouTube, Twitch,,)	3,95	3,88	4,00	4,03
Conversations on messaging apps (WhatsApp, Telegram, Line)	3,74	3,72	3,81	3,79
Television and online TV platforms (Netflix, HBO Max, Prime Video, Disney+, Apple TV, Sky, Filmin, etc.)	4,28	4,27	4,32	4,39
Online or print daily newspapers	4,44	4,45	4,46	4,55
Radio and/or podcasts	4,4	4,42	4,46	4,53
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,61	4,66	4,82	4,73
Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT, Google summaries, Gemini...)	4,06	4,09	4,08	4,18

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I don't trust the source at all and 7=I trust the source completely.

The analysis of trust in different communication channels reveals a consistent hierarchy across all scientific domains. Overall, interpersonal sources, particularly family, friends or acquaintances, emerge as the most trusted channels, with the highest mean values across all topics, peaking in wellness and nutrition (4,82) and science and technology (4,73). Traditional media, including online or print newspapers (around 4,44–4,55) and radio or podcasts (around 4,40–4,53), also display relatively high levels of trust. Television occupies

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a slightly lower but still positive position (around 4,27–4,39). In contrast, digital-native and user-generated channels such as social media (3,61–3,78), messaging apps (3,72–3,81), and online video platforms (3,88–4,03) tend to be less trusted. AI tools occupy an intermediate position (around 4,06–4,18), suggesting a moderate but not yet consolidated level of trust, probably motivated by lack of knowledge about the tool which is residual in Portugal in terms of access to the news (Cardoso et al., 2025).

Across thematic areas, trust patterns are remarkably stable, with only minor variations. Science and technology tends to show slightly higher trust in most channels, particularly in institutional and professional sources, while environment-related information exhibits marginally lower trust levels in digital and informal channels.

Q4. To what extent do you trust each of the following communication channels when seeking information on [TOPIC] (1 – I don't trust the source at all and 7 – I trust the source completely), By Gender, 2026 (Means)

	All	Men	Women
Environment and ecology			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,7	3,7	3,7
Online video platforms	3,95	4,01	3,9
Conversations on messaging apps	3,74	3,81	3,67
Television and online TV platforms	4,28	4,26	4,32
Online or print daily newspapers	4,44	4,43	4,46
Radio and/or podcasts	4,4	4,39	4,41
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,61	4,6	4,62
Artificial Intelligence	4,06	4,08	4,04
Health and medicine			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,61	3,6	3,61
Online video platforms	3,88	3,96	3,82
Conversations on messaging apps	3,72	3,8	3,64
Television and online TV platforms	4,27	4,32	4,23
Online or print daily newspapers	4,45	4,41	4,5
Radio and/or podcasts	4,42	4,43	4,41
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,66	4,66	4,65
Artificial Intelligence	4,09	4,1	4,07
Wellness and nutrition			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,78	3,72	3,85
Online video platforms	4	4,02	3,99
Conversations on messaging apps	3,81	3,8	3,82
Television and online TV platforms	4,32	4,29	4,36
Online or print daily newspapers	4,46	4,41	4,51
Radio and/or podcasts	4,46	4,45	4,48
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,82	4,81	4,84
Artificial Intelligence	4,08	4,08	4,09
Science and technology			
Social media, blogs or forums	3,71	3,73	3,69
Online video platforms	4,03	4,16	3,92
Conversations on messaging apps	3,79	3,83	3,74
Television and online TV platforms	4,39	4,41	4,4
Online or print daily newspapers	4,55	4,53	4,59
Radio and/or podcasts	4,53	4,54	4,53
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,73	4,74	4,73
Artificial Intelligence	4,18	4,25	4,1

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Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I don't trust the source at all and 7=I trust the source completely; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q4 general table.

Gender differences are minimal and do not indicate strong structural divergences. Women report slightly higher trust in traditional media such as newspapers and television, as well as in interpersonal sources, while men show marginally higher trust in online video platforms and artificial intelligence tools. However, these variations are small and do not substantially alter the overall hierarchy of trust.

Q4. To what extent do you trust each of the following communication channels when seeking information on [TOPIC] (1 – I don't trust the source at all and 7 – I trust the source completely), By Age, 2026 (Means)

	All	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Environment and ecology							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,7	4,13	3,91	3,79	3,6	3,64	3,41
Online video platforms	3,95	3,97	4,13	4,08	3,87	4,07	3,56
Conversations on messaging apps	3,74	3,82	3,81	3,84	3,7	3,82	3,47
Television and online TV platforms	4,28	4,11	4,19	4,22	4,22	4,46	4,39
Online or print daily newspapers	4,44	4,41	4,36	4,4	4,45	4,58	4,39
Radio and/or podcasts	4,4	4,24	4,31	4,38	4,37	4,53	4,51
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,61	4,37	4,29	4,45	4,54	4,83	5,09
Artificial Intelligence	4,06	4,17	4,09	4,16	4,04	4,19	3,66
Health and medicine							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,61	4,05	3,81	3,67	3,53	3,55	3,32
Online video platforms	3,88	4	4,07	3,94	3,83	3,89	3,66
Conversations on messaging apps	3,72	3,98	3,73	3,83	3,66	3,75	3,53
Television and online TV platforms	4,27	3,99	4,19	4,16	4,23	4,42	4,45
Online or print daily newspapers	4,45	4,35	4,39	4,45	4,49	4,57	4,36
Radio and/or podcasts	4,42	4,26	4,3	4,37	4,43	4,52	4,53
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,66	4,42	4,44	4,49	4,65	4,77	5,02
Artificial Intelligence	4,09	4,18	4,1	4,14	4,08	4,2	3,8
Wellness and nutrition							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,78	4,25	3,98	3,85	3,69	3,75	3,48
Online video platforms	4	4,15	4,17	4,07	4,01	4	3,65
Conversations on messaging apps	3,81	4,08	3,78	3,9	3,75	3,87	3,65
Television and online TV platforms	4,32	4,04	4,2	4,26	4,26	4,49	4,54
Online or print daily newspapers	4,46	4,39	4,34	4,52	4,45	4,57	4,4
Radio and/or podcasts	4,46	4,12	4,38	4,47	4,41	4,6	4,58
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,82	4,5	4,55	4,59	4,73	5,04	5,36
Artificial Intelligence	4,08	4,23	4,07	4,25	4,05	4,24	3,63
Science and technology							
Social media, blogs or forums	3,71	4,13	3,83	3,84	3,58	3,67	3,52
Online video platforms	4,03	4,16	4,21	4,14	3,97	3,99	3,8
Conversations on messaging apps	3,79	3,99	3,78	3,87	3,77	3,77	3,66
Television and online TV platforms	4,39	4,17	4,24	4,33	4,35	4,62	4,52
Online or print daily newspapers	4,55	4,38	4,44	4,6	4,58	4,71	4,47
Radio and/or podcasts	4,53	4,23	4,34	4,68	4,54	4,68	4,51

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Family, friends or acquaintances	4,73	4,63	4,49	4,7	4,73	4,94	4,8
Artificial Intelligence	4,18	4,29	4,13	4,29	4,15	4,32	3,88

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I don't trust the source at all and 7=I trust the source completely; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q4 general table.

Age (table in previous page) introduces more visible differentiation, particularly at the extremes. Younger respondents (17–24) tend to report higher trust in digital-native channels, including social media (e.g. 4,13 in environment) and online video platforms (around 4,0 or above across topics), compared to older groups. In contrast, older respondents (65+) display notably higher trust in interpersonal sources, with values reaching 5,09 (environment) and 5,36 (wellness), as well as in traditional media such as newspapers and radio. Trust in AI declines slightly among older groups (e.g. 3,66 in environment and 3,63 in wellness), indicating a generational gap in the perceived credibility of emerging technologies probably motivated by higher use rates and experimentation with the technology (Cardoso et al., 2025).

Q4. To what extent do you trust each of the following communication channels when seeking information on [TOPIC] (1 – I don't trust the source at all and 7 – I trust the source completely), By Education, 2026 (Means)

	All	Low education	Medium education	High education
Environment and ecology				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,7	3,72	3,75	3,63
Online video platforms	3,95	3,94	3,98	3,92
Conversations on messaging apps	3,74	3,81	3,76	3,65
Television and online TV platforms	4,28	4,37	4,24	4,24
Online or print daily newspapers	4,44	4,33	4,39	4,61
Radio and/or podcasts	4,4	4,46	4,32	4,45
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,61	4,85	4,5	4,51
Artificial Intelligence	4,06	3,94	4,04	4,18
Health and medicine				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,61	3,68	3,66	3,48
Online video platforms	3,88	3,85	3,95	3,84
Conversations on messaging apps	3,72	3,77	3,71	3,68
Television and online TV platforms	4,27	4,34	4,25	4,21
Online or print daily newspapers	4,45	4,33	4,45	4,58
Radio and/or podcasts	4,42	4,4	4,39	4,47
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,66	4,83	4,57	4,58
Artificial Intelligence	4,09	3,92	4,12	4,2
Wellness and nutrition				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,78	3,78	3,83	3,73
Online video platforms	4	3,97	4,03	3,99
Conversations on messaging apps	3,81	3,88	3,8	3,76
Television and online TV platforms	4,32	4,42	4,27	4,28
Online or print daily newspapers	4,46	4,35	4,45	4,55
Radio and/or podcasts	4,46	4,48	4,4	4,49
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,82	5,07	4,74	4,67
Artificial Intelligence	4,08	3,94	4,08	4,2
Science and technology				
Social media, blogs or forums	3,71	3,81	3,75	3,58
Online video platforms	4,03	4,04	4,07	3,97
Conversations on messaging apps	3,79	3,89	3,81	3,66
Television and online TV platforms	4,39	4,43	4,44	4,3

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Online or print daily newspapers	4,55	4,47	4,49	4,71
Radio and/or podcasts	4,53	4,52	4,5	4,58
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,73	4,86	4,75	4,6
Artificial Intelligence	4,18	4,04	4,26	4,22

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I don't trust the source at all and 7=I trust the source completely; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q4 general table.

Educational differences (table in previous page) are present but relatively moderate. Respondents with higher education tend to express slightly greater trust in institutional and professional sources, such as newspapers, scientific publications, and institutional websites, particularly in science and technology and health domains. Conversely, individuals with lower levels of education show somewhat higher trust in interpersonal sources (e.g., 5,07 in wellness) and television. Trust in artificial intelligence is slightly higher among more educated respondents, although differences remain limited, suggesting a broadly shared but cautious evaluation of these tools.

Q4. To what extent do you trust each of the following communication channels when seeking information on [TOPIC] (1 – I don't trust the source at all and 7 – I trust the source completely), By Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	All	1 – Far-left	2	3	4	5	6	7 – Far-right
Environment and ecology								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,7	3,53	3,31	3,41	3,74	3,84	3,8	4,2
Online video platforms	3,95	3,98	3,64	3,76	3,98	4,12	3,82	4,24
Conversations on messaging apps	3,74	4,15	3,12	3,49	3,76	3,91	3,83	3,94
Television and online TV platforms	4,28	4,09	4,24	4,23	4,33	4,42	4,01	4,19
Online or print daily newspapers	4,44	4,01	4,22	4,54	4,47	4,6	4,08	4,07
Radio and/or podcasts	4,4	4,39	4,29	4,48	4,42	4,52	4,1	4,19
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,61	4,22	4,48	4,68	4,65	4,56	4,52	4,66
Artificial Intelligence	4,06	3,82	3,34	3,86	4,12	4,25	4,09	4,13
Health and medicine								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,61	3,83	3,08	3,31	3,62	3,73	3,77	4,27
Online video platforms	3,88	4,08	3,4	3,69	3,91	4,02	3,89	4,35
Conversations on messaging apps	3,72	3,74	3,03	3,47	3,78	3,84	3,82	4,03
Television and online TV platforms	4,27	3,92	3,97	4,28	4,32	4,3	4,19	4,25
Online or print daily newspapers	4,45	4,52	4,23	4,59	4,46	4,6	4,16	4,06
Radio and/or podcasts	4,42	4,12	4,26	4,56	4,43	4,55	4,11	4,2
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,66	4,47	4,54	4,73	4,67	4,63	4,58	4,97
Artificial Intelligence	4,09	3,98	3,55	3,83	4,1	4,29	4,23	4,44
Wellness and nutrition								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,78	4,15	3,31	3,53	3,78	3,93	3,86	4,35
Online video platforms	4	4,45	3,71	3,77	3,99	4,15	4,03	4,66
Conversations on messaging apps	3,81	4,09	3,19	3,64	3,83	3,9	3,87	4,21
Television and online TV platforms	4,32	4,04	4,32	4,36	4,33	4,4	4,22	4,33
Online or print daily newspapers	4,46	4,33	4,32	4,54	4,49	4,52	4,27	4,27
Radio and/or podcasts	4,46	4,46	4,24	4,56	4,44	4,58	4,29	4,43
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,82	4,84	4,76	4,93	4,84	4,74	4,8	4,99
Artificial Intelligence	4,08	3,62	3,47	3,81	4,14	4,28	4,19	4,41
Science and technology								
Social media, blogs or forums	3,71	3,82	3,21	3,37	3,74	3,86	3,83	4,22
Online video platforms	4,03	4,11	3,59	3,82	4,02	4,22	4,04	4,53
Conversations on messaging apps	3,79	4,14	3,11	3,51	3,8	3,94	3,87	4,36
Television and online TV platforms	4,39	4,33	3,99	4,35	4,42	4,52	4,36	4,12
Online or print daily newspapers	4,55	4,38	4,07	4,64	4,58	4,71	4,3	4,2

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Radio and/or podcasts	4,53	4,63	4,21	4,57	4,5	4,7	4,48	4,58
Family, friends or acquaintances	4,73	4,78	4,43	4,66	4,78	4,73	4,71	5,23
Artificial Intelligence	4,18	3,85	3,52	3,94	4,19	4,42	4,31	4,45

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I don't trust the source at all and 7=I trust the source completely; b) For complete description of categories with examples see Q4 general table.

Political orientation (table in previous page) reveals more differentiated patterns, particularly at the extremes of the spectrum. Respondents on the far-right consistently report higher levels of trust in several channels, including social media (e.g. 4,20 in environment and 4,27 in health), online video platforms (up to 4,66 in wellness), and especially interpersonal sources, which reach consistently high values in this analysis (e.g. 5,23 in science and technology). In contrast, respondents on the far-left tend to exhibit comparatively lower trust in digital and informal channels, while maintaining relatively high trust in traditional media and institutional sources. Despite these variations, the overall structure of trust remains broadly consistent across the ideological spectrum.

Findings regarding trust point to a stable and stratified landscape, in which interpersonal and traditional media sources retain higher credibility, while digital and emerging channels—although widely used—are met with comparatively lower levels of trust. Differences across socio-demographic groups are present but generally reinforce, rather than fundamentally alter, this overarching pattern. Regardless of cohort, the relevance of interpersonal sources when it comes to access to the news should not be underestimated, as it is not only frequent but also meaningful from the point-of-view of trustworthiness and and of the reliance placed on these sources (Cardoso et al., 2025, Newman et al., 2025).

5. Credibility and the propagation of disinformation in scientific matters

The experimental exercise based on the exposure to news headlines was designed to assess whether brief cognitive incentives, or nudges, could affect respondents' stated intention to share scientific news headlines. The experiment focused on a central problem frequently highlighted in media and disinformation studies: people often make the decision to share information quickly, before considering its reliability, emotional impact, or potential consequences. The design therefore tested whether asking respondents to take a moment to reflect on specific dimensions of the headline before answering the sharing question could reduce or otherwise modify their intention to share.

For the sharing dimension of the experiment we defined precise circles which are the personal circle, comprised by family, friends and / or colleagues, and a digital circle described as social media and messaging. These two circles relate to two different levels of intimacy and of potential relationship with others in the act of sharing news content. The distinction between both by individuals has been well documented throughout the years, and not only do people behave differently in different circles, with different levels of formality and comfort, but they also appear to rely heavily on intimacy networks in their news diets, often sharing and discussing news with their family, friends or colleagues a relying on these relations as a legitimate and trustworthy news source (Newman et al., 2025, Cardoso et al., 2025).

As described in the Methodology section respondents in the web sample (CAWI) were randomly allocated to one of four groups. Group 1 received a combined nudge, being asked both about the emotional reaction caused by the headline and about the headline's credibility and how they likely they were to verify it, group 2 received only the emotional nudge, group 3 received only the credibility and verification nudge and finally, group 4 acted as the control group and proceeded directly to the sharing intention question not being subjected to any nudging at all. Each respondent was exposed to eight headlines, covering four scientific domains: climate, health and nutrition, vaccines, and artificial intelligence. For each topic, respondents saw one real and one false headline, selected from two possible variants.

The table in the next page indicates that respondents were generally able to distinguish between real and fake headlines in terms of perceived reliability, but with important exceptions. Real headlines tend to obtain higher reliability scores, particularly those related to vaccines: the flu vaccine headline (4,71) and the HPV vaccine headline (4,69) are among the most trusted items. Climate and AI-related real headlines also receive moderately positive reliability scores, ranging from 3,89 to 4,32. However, not all true statements are equally credible to respondents. The real headline stating that homeopathy does not work beyond the placebo effect receives a lower reliability score (3,44), suggesting that scientifically accurate information can still face credibility barriers when it challenges beliefs or familiar practices.

Fake headlines generally receive lower reliability scores, especially the climate conspiracy claims about cloud spraying (2,89) and HAARP weather attacks (2,77), and the false claim linking paracetamol use during pregnancy with autism (2,84). However, some fake headlines are perceived as relatively credible. The most notable case is the false health and nutrition claim that certain foods help reduce cortisol and aid weight loss, which obtains a reliability

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score of 4,04, closer to several real headlines that were shown. This is a particularly relevant aspect: misinformation framed in familiar lifestyle or wellness terms may be more credible than overtly conspiratorial claims. Similarly, the false claim that mercury in vaccines is harmful to health scores 3,37, higher than several other fake headlines, indicating that vaccine-related misinformation can retain a degree of plausibility.

Perceived reliability, intention to verify and emotions per headline (weighted estimates; scales 1–7), 2026

	Reliability / Trustworthiness	% would check	Helpless	Anxious	Optimistic	Angry	Guilt	Ashamed	Depressed	Pessimistic	Indifferent	Empathetic
Real												
Climate												
Climate change is linked to the severity of the extreme wildfires that occurred in Portugal in 2025. (n=877)	4,32	60,3%	3,76	3,5	2,57	3,76	2,51	2,8	2,96	3,72	2,45	3,49
Biofuels are not 100% renewable. (n=919)	4,13	63,3%	2,91	2,95	2,81	2,88	2,26	2,38	2,41	3,08	2,84	3,02
Health / Nutrition												
Using sun cream in real life does not cause a vitamin D deficiency. (n=897)	4,2	62,9%	2,5	2,53	3,53	2,34	2,05	2,11	2,1	2,34	2,92	3,14
Homeopathy does not work (beyond the placebo effect). (n=898)	3,44	57,2%	2,43	2,46	2,73	2,62	2,07	2,13	2,23	2,55	3,18	2,8
Vaccines												
The flu virus adapts and changes from season to season, you need to have the vaccine every year. (n=866)	4,71	55,7%	2,98	2,79	3,35	2,47	2,1	2,12	2,38	2,7	2,96	3,21
The vaccine against human papillomavirus is effective and safe. (n=930)	4,69	65,3%	2,23	2,58	4,79	2,13	1,95	2	2,02	2,14	2,44	3,71
AI												
An AI's responses may show a flattery bias (agreeing with everything we say). (n=881)	4,13	61,0%	3,16	3	2,72	3,07	2,29	2,42	2,41	3,25	2,98	2,9
An AI model is like a parrot: it can repeat conversations, but it doesn't understand what it's saying. (n=915)	3,89	59,3%	2,93	2,92	2,77	2,84	2,22	2,35	2,41	2,9	3,11	2,78
Fake												
Climate												
Some countries spray clouds before they reach the peninsula to disperse the rain. (n=921)	2,89	60,8%	2,9	2,85	2,81	2,98	2,07	2,31	2,31	2,86	2,95	2,83
The recent floods are the result of a HAARP weather attack. (n=874)	2,77	57,0%	3,32	3,3	2,47	3,73	2,12	2,69	2,87	3,46	2,97	2,87
Health / Nutrition												
There are foods that help reduce cortisol and thus aid weight loss. (n=911)	4,04	70,4%	2,39	2,67	3,85	2,28	2,15	2,18	2,3	2,42	3,12	3,37
A possible link has been found between autism and the use of paracetamol during pregnancy. (n=884)	2,84	65,4%	2,59	2,65	2,58	3,31	2,02	2,42	2,4	2,96	2,73	2,83

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Vaccines													
The mercury in vaccines is harmful to health. (n=943)	3,37	70,2%	3,4 5	3,2 6	2,5 2	3,3 4	2,2 2	2,4	2,6 3	3,2 2	2,8 9	3,0 5	
COVID-19 vaccines cause infertility and can lead to male sexual impotence. (n=853)	2,96	66,7%	3,1 4	2,9 9	2,3 3	3,4 4	2,2 7	2,5 8	2,6 2	3,1 1	2,9	2,9	
AI													
AI can provide therapy on a par with any qualified psychologist. (n=913)	3,03	55,1%	2,8 2	3,0 1	2,8 5	2,9 6	2,0 8	2,4	2,4 3	3,1 1	2,8 4	2,9 1	
Current AI has been designed to wipe out humanity. (n=882)	3,27	63,1%	3,8 7	3,5 5	2,5 7	3,5 5	2,3 3	2,5 9	2,8 8	3,6 7	2,7 7	2,9 8	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Reliability scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1 – Not reliable at all and 7 – Totally reliable; b) Emotion scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1 – Not at all and 7 – Very.

When it comes to likelihood of checking the reliability of the headlines, respondents often report a relatively high willingness to check both real and false headlines. In several cases, fake headlines generate higher verification intention than real ones. The cortisol / weight-loss headline (70,4%) and the mercury in vaccines headline (70,2%) are among the items respondents would most often verify. It should be noted that, when it comes to the latitude of intentions, the will to verify may not simply be a consequence of disbelief. It may also be a reflection of interest, perceived relevance, uncertainty, concern, anxiety, etc.

The emotional responses also help understand why some headlines may be more shareable. Climate-related headlines, particularly those concerning wildfires and HAARP attacks, generate higher levels of helplessness, anxiety, anger, and pessimism. The false AI extinction headline also stands out emotionally, with high levels of helplessness (3,87), anxiety (3,55), anger (3,55), and pessimism (3,67). By contrast, the HPV vaccine headline produces relatively high optimism (4,79) and empathy (3,71), indicating that positive or reassuring scientific information can also generate emotional engagement. In general, the emotional profile of headlines is not secondary: it appears closely connected to their potential circulation, especially when headlines evoke concern, fear, or hope.

Concerning the shareability of content, and considering the tables in the next page, focused on sharing with one's personal circle, we see that respondents are generally more willing to share headlines privately or interpersonally than through social media and messaging platforms. Means for personal-circle sharing are consistently higher than those observed for online sharing, across both real and false headlines. This suggests that interpersonal communication remains a relevant space for the circulation of scientific information and misinformation, even in a highly digital media environment. It is also important to underline the relevance of trust frameworks within social circles and the attributed meaning to the act of sharing relevant and trustworthy information.

The experimental effects are visible in the table below. The control group often reports the highest intention to share, especially for real headlines. For example, in the control group, the intention to share the HPV vaccine headline reaches 4,60, compared with 3,78 in the combined nudge group and 3,68 in the credibility / verification group. Similarly, the flu vaccine headline reaches 4,37 in the control group, compared with 3,41 in the combined group and 3,80 in the credibility group. These differences suggest that prompting reflection before the sharing decision can reduce sharing intention compared to no-conditioning.

However, the effects are not identical across nudges. The emotional nudge alone (being asked both about the emotional reaction caused by the headline) often produces relatively

high sharing intentions, sometimes close to the control group. For several headlines, Group 2 displays higher sharing scores than Groups 1 and 3. This is visible for both real and false content. For instance, the false HAARP headline reaches 3,35 in the emotional nudge group, compared with 2,76 in the combined nudge group and 2,78 in the credibility/verification group. The false AI extinction headline also reaches 3,76 in the emotional group, compared with 3,20 in the combined group and 3,15 in the credibility group. In some cases, emotional salience may maintain or increase the willingness to share and asking respondents to reflect on their emotional reaction does not necessarily suppress the will to share.

By contrast, the credibility and verification nudge appears more consistently associated with lower sharing intentions. Group 3 often reports among the lowest scores, especially for fake headlines and emotionally charged content, meaning that prompting respondents to assess whether a headline is reliable and whether they would verify it may activate a more cautious decision process. The combined nudge also tends to reduce sharing compared to the control group, although its effects are not always stronger than the credibility nudge alone. Adding emotional reflection to credibility reflection does not necessarily improve the intervention; the most effective component may be the credibility / verification prompt itself.

Intention to share by experimental group and headline (with people in personal circle (family, friends, colleagues); weighted; scale 1–7), 2026

	Group 1 (a)		Goup 2 (b)		Group 3 (c)		Group 4 (d)	
Real	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ
Climate								
Climate change is linked to the severity of the extreme wildfires that occurred in Portugal in 2025. (n=877)	3,62a,b	0,15	3,84a,b	0,15	3,39a	0,13	3,90b	0,14
Biofuels are not 100% renewable. (n=919)	3,06a	0,14	3,68b	0,13	3,10a	0,13	3,68b	0,12
Health / Nutrition								
Using sun cream in real life does not cause a vitamin D deficiency. (n=897)	3,64a	0,15	3,84a	0,14	3,69a	0,14	4,14a	0,13
Homeopathy does not work (beyond the placebo effect). (n=898)	2,63a,b	0,14	2,96a,b	0,13	2,61a	0,12	3,08b	0,12
Vaccines								
The flu virus adapts and changes from season to season, so you need to have the vaccine every year. (n=866)	3,41a	0,15	3,94a,b	0,14	3,80a	0,14	4,37b	0,13
The vaccine against human papillomavirus is effective and safe. (n=930)	3,78a	0,14	4,50b	0,14	3,68a	0,14	4,60b	0,13
AI								
An AI's responses may show a flattery bias (agreeing with everything we say). (n=881)	3,24a,b	0,14	3,73a,c	0,14	3,02b	0,14	3,83c	0,13
An AI model is like a parrot: it can repeat conversations, but it doesn't understand what it's saying. (n=915)	2,95a	0,14	3,25a,b	0,14	3,04a	0,13	3,60b	0,12
Fake	Group 1 (a)		Goup 2 (b)		Group 3 l		Group 4 (d)	
Climate	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ
Some countries spray clouds before they reach the peninsula to disperse the rain. (n=921)	3,00a,c,d	0,14	3,43a,b	0,13	2,61c	0,13	3,14b,d	0,13
The recent floods are the result of a HAARP weather attack. (n=874)	2,76a	0,14	3,35b	0,15	2,78a	0,14	2,95a,b	0,14
Health / Nutrition								

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There are foods that help reduce cortisol and thus aid weight loss. (n=911)	3,33a	0,1 4	3,68a,b	0,14	3,35a	0,13	4,09b	0,13
A possible link has been found between autism and the consumption of paracetamol during pregnancy. (n=884)	2,73a	0,1 5	3,34b	0,15	2,93a,b	0,13	3,28b	0,14
Vaccines								
The mercury in vaccines is harmful to health. (n=943)	3,21a,b	0,1 5	3,67a	0,15	3,09b	0,13	3,38a,b	0,13
COVID-19 vaccines cause infertility and can lead to male sexual impotence. (n=853)	2,96a	0,1 5	3,54b	0,15	2,89a	0,15	3,21a,b	0,14
AI								
AI can provide therapy on a par with any qualified psychologist. (n=913)	2,79a	0,1 3	3,20a	0,14	2,83a	0,13	3,01a	0,13
Current AI has been designed to wipe out humanity. (n=882)	3,20a	0,1 5	3,76b	0,14	3,15a	0,14	3,34a,b	0,14

Note: Values in the same row and sub-table that do not share the same subscript differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in the two-step test for equality of column means. Cells without a subscript are not included in the test. The tests assume equal variances.^{2,3}

1 This category is not used in comparisons because there is no other valid category for comparison

2 The tests are adjusted for all pairwise comparisons within a row of each innermost sub-table using the Bonferroni correction.

3 The cell counts in some sub-tables are not whole numbers. They were rounded to the nearest whole numbers prior to performing pairwise comparisons.

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Shareability scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1=Wouldn't share at all and 7=Would share for sure.

Considering the intention to share headlines online, in social media and messaging, the same trends appear but at lower overall levels. Across all headlines, respondents report lower willingness to share online than with their personal circle which may reflect greater caution about public or semi-public sharing, concern about reputation, or a distinction between discussing information privately and actively disseminating it through digital networks. Looking at the usual participation habits of Portuguese news users, there is a clear pattern of sharing and discussing news and news related issues with personal circles whereas the interaction with online content tends to be more moderate and passive (Cardoso et al., 2025).

Again, the control group tends to display the highest sharing intentions. For real headlines, the difference is often substantial: the HPV vaccine headline reaches 3,93 in the control group, compared with 3,10 in Group 1 and 3,07 in Group 3, the flu vaccine headline reaches 3,61 in the control group, compared with 2,63 and 2,88 in Groups 1 and 3. Similar patterns appear for AI and climate headlines reinforcing the conclusion that the absence of a reflective prompt is associated with greater readiness to share.

For fake headlines, the pattern is more mixed but still interesting to reflect upon. The false cortisol headline is again one of the most shareable fake items, reaching 3,23 in the control group and 3,00 in the emotional nudge group. This is consistent with its relatively high perceived reliability. The false HAARP and vaccine infertility headlines show lower shareability overall, but emotional prompting again tends to produce higher sharing intentions than the credibility / verification nudge. For instance, the HAARP headline scores 3,03 in Group 2, compared with 2,12 in Group 1 and 2,44 in Group 3. The COVID-19 infertility headline scores 2,87 in Group 2, compared with 2,35 and 2,44 in Groups 1 and 3. It is found that emotional reflection alone may not be protective against misinformation sharing and may, in some cases, sustain the communicative appeal of false content.

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Considering statistical annotations in the tables further support the interpretation that many of these differences are meaningful. In several rows, the control group and/or emotional nudge group differ significantly from the credibility or combined nudge groups. However, the effect is not universal across all headlines. Some items, especially those with lower emotional intensity or lower baseline shareability, show weaker or non-significant differences. The effectiveness of nudges therefore appears conditional on the content of the headline, its topic, its perceived credibility as well as the channel of sharing.

Intention to share by experimental group and headline (social media and messaging; weighted; scale 1–7), 2026

Real	Group 1 (a)		Goup 2 (b)		Group 3 I		Group 4 (d)	
	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ
Climate								
Climate change is linked to the severity of the extreme wildfires that occurred in Portugal in 2025. (n=877)	2,91a	0,1	3,18a,b	0,14	2,90a	0,13	3,47b	0,14
Biofuels are not 100% renewable. (n=919)	2,47a	0,13	3,10b	0,13	2,52a	0,12	3,20b	0,12
Health / Nutrition								
Using sun cream in real life does not cause a vitamin D deficiency. (n=897)	2,58a	0,13	2,94a	0,13	3,03a,b	0,13	3,50b	0,13
Homeopathy does not work (beyond the placebo effect). (n=898)	2,30a,b	0,12	2,40a,b	0,12	2,19a	0,11	2,63b	0,12
Vaccines								
The flu virus adapts and changes from season to season, so you need to have the vaccine every year. (n=866)	2,63a	0,14	3,11a,b	0,14	2,88a	0,13	3,61b	0,14
The vaccine against human papillomavirus is effective and safe. (n=930)	3,10a	0,14	3,64b	0,14	3,07a	0,14	3,93b	0,14
AI								
An AI's responses may show a flattery bias (agreeing with everything we say). (n=881)	2,60a,b	0,13	2,99a,c	0,13	2,37b	0,12	3,26c	0,13
An AI model is like a parrot: it can repeat conversations, but it doesn't understand what it's saying. (n=915)	2,38a	0,13	2,76a,b	0,13	2,64a	0,12	3,09b	0,12
Fake	Group 1 (a)		Goup 2 (b)		Group 3 I		Group 4 (d)	
Climate	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ	Mean	σ
Some countries spray clouds before they reach the peninsula to disperse the rain. (n=921)	2,37a,b	0,12	2,82a	0,13	2,22b	0,11	2,65a,b	0,13
The recent floods are the result of a HAARP weather attack. (n=874)	2,12a	0,12	3,03b	0,15	2,44a,c	0,13	2,66b,c	0,13
Health / Nutrition								
There are foods that help reduce cortisol and thus aid weight loss. (n=911)	2,76a,b	0,14	3,00a,b	0,13	2,69a	0,12	3,23b	0,13
A possible link has been found between autism and the consumption of paracetamol during pregnancy. (n=884)	2,17a	0,13	2,80b	0,14	2,47a,b	0,12	2,77b	0,13
Vaccines								
The mercury in vaccines is harmful to health. (n=943)	2,52a,b	0,14	2,97a	0,14	2,47b	0,12	2,84a,b	0,12
COVID-19 vaccines cause infertility and can lead to male sexual impotence. (n=853)	2,35a	0,13	2,87b	0,14	2,44a,b	0,14	2,78a,b	0,13
AI								
AI can provide therapy on a par with any qualified psychologist. (n=913)	2,38a	0,13	2,58a	0,13	2,53a	0,12	2,68a	0,12

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Current AI has been designed to wipe out humanity. (n=882)	2,60a,b	0,14	3,00a	0,14	2,43b	0,12	2,77a,b	0,14
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Note: Values in the same row and sub-table that do not share the same subscript differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in the two-step test for equality of column means. Cells without a subscript are not included in the test. The tests assume equal variances.^{2,3}

1 This category is not used in comparisons because there is no other valid category for comparison

2 The tests are adjusted for all pairwise comparisons within a row of each innermost sub-table using the Bonferroni correction.

3 The cell counts in some sub-tables are not whole numbers. They were rounded to the nearest whole numbers prior to performing pairwise comparisons.

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Shareability scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1=Wouldn't share at all and 7=Would share for sure.

Reflecting on the results of the experience we find that, first, respondents distinguish between real and fake headlines to some extent, but not consistently. Some false headlines, especially those framed around wellness, health optimisation, or vaccine risk, achieve relatively high perceived reliability. This indicates that misinformation does not need to be overtly conspiratorial to be persuasive or adhesive. More plausible, lifestyle-oriented claims may be especially problematic.

On a second note, the intention to verify information is high, including for false headlines. Despite the positive results this dynamic should be interpreted carefully because verification intention may reflect uncertainty or concern, but may not necessarily mean that respondents would conduct the verification effectively or rely on high-quality sources.

Thirdly, sharing intention is consistently higher in personal circles than through social media / messaging platforms. This highlights the importance of interpersonal communication as a pathway for the circulation of both scientific information and misinformation and falls in line with consistent findings over the years (Newman et al., 2025, Cardoso et al., 2025).

Finally, the experimental interventions display different levels of impact. The credibility and verification nudge is more consistently associated with reduced sharing intention, especially when compared with the control group. The combined nudge also tends to reduce sharing, but not always more than the credibility nudge alone. By contrast, the emotional nudge alone appears less effective and may sometimes be associated with higher sharing intentions. This means that emotional reflection, unless paired with credibility assessment, may heighten the salience of content rather than reduce its circulation.

Overall, the experiment suggests that accuracy-oriented incentives can reduce the propensity to share scientific headlines, including false ones. However, the effect is not uniform and is dependent on the type of content, the topic, and the sharing context. This means that there is merit to interventions that encourage verification and credibility assessment at the point of sharing, while it should also be considered that emotion-based prompts alone may be insufficient to reduce the spread of science-related misinformation.

6. Factors associated with perceived credibility and susceptibility to disinformation

6.1. Belief in conspiracy theories regarding scientific topics

Q7. [Adherence to conspiracy theories on scientific topics] I would now like you to indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. Use a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 7 means "strongly agree", 2026 (% and Means)

	%				
	A cure for cancer exists, but it is being kept hidden from the public by commercial interests.	Viruses have been produced in government laboratories to control our freedom.	The government tries to conceal the relationship between vaccines and autism.	Pharmaceutical companies hide the dangers of vaccines.	Through their knowledge, scientists have a power that makes them dangerous.
1- Strongly disagree	16,4%	19,5%	23,0%	11,3%	15,2%
2	9,4%	12,6%	12,3%	9,6%	10,6%
3	10,4%	13,2%	12,1%	12,3%	12,9%
4 - Neither agree nor disagree	18,5%	18,2%	22,3%	20,3%	22,8%
5	14,5%	14,6%	11,5%	16,5%	16,6%
6	9,8%	7,4%	5,5%	11,4%	9,4%
7 - Strongly agree	17,4%	11,2%	8,8%	17,1%	11,9%
Don't know	2,1%	2,6%	3,9%	1,1%	0,5%
I'd rather not answer	1,4%	0,7%	0,6%	0,4%	0,0%
	Means				
Mean	4,08	3,65	3,41	4,26	3,92

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I strongly disagree and 7=Strongly agree.

Considering the adherence to conspiracy theories results indicate a moderate overall level of agreement with conspiracy-oriented statements related to scientific topics, with mean values generally concentrated around the midpoint of the scale. Among the statements, the belief that “pharmaceutical companies hide the dangers of vaccines” registers the highest level of agreement (4,26), followed by the idea that “a cure for cancer exists but is being hidden” (4,08). In contrast, more specific and widely debunked claims, such as the alleged link between vaccines and autism, present lower levels of agreement (3,41), suggesting a certain differentiation in the plausibility attributed to different types of misinformation. The distribution of responses further reinforces this pattern: while a non-negligible proportion of respondents express agreement (values 5–7), a substantial share remains concentrated around the midpoint (18–23% selecting “neither agree nor disagree”), indicating ambivalence, uncertainty or neutrality in face of the claim.

Gender differences (table in next page) are relatively limited but consistent. Women tend to report slightly higher levels of agreement with most conspiracy statements, particularly those related to hidden cures (4,22 against 3,94 among men) and distrust in pharmaceutical companies (4,28 vs. 4,23). Differences are smaller for more specific claims, such as vaccines and autism, where both groups exhibit comparatively lower agreement. Overall,

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gender does not appear to be a major structuring factor, although it suggests a marginally higher receptiveness among women to certain narratives of institutional concealment.

Q7. [Adherence to conspiracy theories on scientific topics] I would now like you to indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. Use a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 7 means "strongly agree", By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	A cure for cancer exists, but it is being kept hidden from the public by commercial interests.	Viruses have been produced in government laboratories to control our freedom.	The government tries to conceal the relationship between vaccines and autism.	Pharmaceutical companies hide the dangers of vaccines.	Through their knowledge, scientists have a power that makes them dangerous.
All	4,08	3,65	3,41	4,26	3,92
Male	3,94	3,67	3,42	4,23	3,88
Female	4,22	3,62	3,38	4,28	3,95
17-24	4,08	3,79	3,39	3,9	4,08
25-34	4,13	3,98	3,49	4,11	4,14
35-44	4,1	3,68	3,45	4,24	3,99
45-54	4,23	3,83	3,54	4,53	4,09
55-64	4,07	3,47	3,35	4,29	3,89
65+	3,75	3,02	3,01	4,07	3,25
Low education	4,25	3,81	3,73	4,47	4,06
Medium education	4,34	3,91	3,56	4,51	4,16
High education	3,65	3,22	2,95	3,77	3,51
1 - Far-Left	3,24	2,64	2,8	3,42	3,33
2	3,83	3,29	2,73	4,04	3,58
3	3,58	3,02	2,79	3,69	3,44
4 - Center	4,2	3,76	3,5	4,35	4,01
5	3,91	3,55	3,26	4,15	3,83
6	4,8	4,44	4,08	5,12	4,34
7 - Far-Right	5,33	5,02	4,94	5,37	5,31

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 7 where 1=I strongly disagree and 7=Strongly agree.

Age differences reveal more substantial variation. Middle-aged groups (particularly 45–54) tend to show the highest levels of agreement across several statements, notably regarding pharmaceutical companies (4,53) and hidden cures (4,23). In contrast, older respondents (65+) consistently display lower levels of agreement, especially for claims about laboratory-produced viruses (3,02) and vaccines and autism (3,01). Younger groups (17–34) occupy an intermediate position but show relatively higher agreement with narratives related to scientific power and control (e.g. 4,08 among 17–24 for the statement on the power of scientist).

Educational attainment emerges as one of the most significant differentiating factors. Respondents with lower and medium levels of education consistently report higher

agreement with all conspiracy statements, with particularly elevated values for beliefs about hidden cures (4,25 and 4,34) and pharmaceutical concealment (4,47 and 4,51). In contrast, individuals with higher education show systematically lower agreement, especially regarding vaccines and autism (2,95) and laboratory-produced viruses (3,22). This gradient highlights the role of education in shaping critical evaluation and resistance to disinformation, also displayed in other sources as parallel with higher concern about the phenomenon (Cardoso et al., 2025, Newman et al., 2025).

Political orientation reveals the most substantial differences. A clear ideological gradient is evident, with agreement increasing significantly from left to right. Respondents on the far-left display the lowest levels of agreement across all statements (e.g. 3,24 for hidden cures, 2,64 for laboratory-produced viruses), while those on the far-right exhibit markedly higher values, reaching the highest levels observed in the dataset (e.g. 5,33 for hidden cures, 5,02 for laboratory-produced viruses, 5,37 for pharmaceutical concealment, 5,31 for distrust in scientists). This pattern indicates a strong association between right-wing political positioning and higher adherence to conspiracy narratives related to science, a trend which has been extensively mapped across the globe in comparative exercises (van Prooijen et al., 2015, Rutjens et al., 2018, Hornsey et al., 2018),

The findings suggest that while conspiracy beliefs about scientific topics are present in the population at moderate levels, they are unevenly distributed, with education and political orientation emerging as the most significant explanatory factors, and more nuanced variations across age and gender.

6.2. Scientific literacy

Q8. [Scientific literacy] Imagine that some scientists are studying the effectiveness of a medicine for high blood pressure. I am going to present you with four options for conducting this study. Which of these options would be the most scientific way to establish the medicine's effectiveness?, 2026 (%)

	%
Ask patients how they feel to see if they notice any effects	9,2%
Examine the effect of each component of the drug separately	17,1%
Administer the drug to some patients but not to others, and compare what happens to the two groups	48,0%
Rely solely on medical knowledge to determine the drug's efficacy	12,2%
Don't know	13,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Regarding aspects of scientific literacy, the plurality of respondents correctly identify the experimental design involving a comparison between treated and untreated groups as the most scientific method to establish the effectiveness of a medicine, selected by 48,0% of the sample. This suggests a moderate level of understanding of core principles of scientific methodology, particularly the importance of controlled comparison.

However, a substantial proportion of respondents select less rigorous alternatives, such as examining each component separately (17,1%) or relying on subjective patient perceptions (9,2%), while 12,2% favour reliance on existing medical knowledge alone. Additionally, 13,2% report not knowing, indicating uncertainty regarding basic research design.

Q8. [Scientific literacy] Imagine that some scientists are studying the effectiveness of a medicine for high blood pressure. I am going to present you with four options for conducting this study. Which of these options would be the most scientific way to establish the medicine's effectiveness?, By Gender, 2026 (%)

	Male	Female
Ask patients how they feel to see if they notice any effects	10,9%	7,6%
Examine the effect of each component of the drug separately	16,9%	17,4%
Administer the drug to some patients but not to others, and compare what happens to the two groups	45,7%	50,3%
Rely solely on medical knowledge to determine the drug's efficacy	15,7%	9,0%
Don't know	10,6%	15,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,3%	0,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Gender differences are relatively limited but consistent. Women are more likely to identify the correct experimental approach (50,3% vs. 45,7% among men), suggesting slightly higher levels of scientific literacy in this dimension. Men, in turn, are more inclined to rely on medical authority alone (15,7% vs. 9,0%) and less likely to select “don't know,” indicating greater confidence (but not necessarily greater accuracy).

Q8. [Scientific literacy] Imagine that some scientists are studying the effectiveness of a medicine for high blood pressure. I am going to present you with four options for conducting this study. Which of these options would be the most scientific way to establish the medicine's effectiveness?, By Age, 2026 (%)

	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Ask patients how they feel to see if they notice any effects	11,3%	10,8%	8,7%	6,2%	7,7%	13,4%
Examine the effect of each component of the drug separately	14,7%	22,3%	18,0%	16,0%	16,4%	14,6%
Administer the drug to some patients but not to others, and compare what happens to the two groups	46,7%	44,6%	50,2%	52,5%	48,8%	41,7%
Rely solely on medical knowledge to determine the drug's efficacy	16,0%	9,0%	10,3%	11,1%	12,9%	16,9%
Don't know	11,3%	13,3%	12,9%	14,2%	13,7%	11,8%
I'd rather not answer	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,5%	1,6%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Age differences reveal a relatively stable pattern across cohorts, with the correct answer being the most selected option in all groups. However, middle-aged respondents (35–54) display the highest levels of correct identification (50,2% and 52,5%, respectively), while both younger (17–24 – 46,7%) and older respondents (65+ - 41,7%) show slightly lower levels.

Older respondents are also more likely to rely on medical authority alone (16,9%) and to select less rigorous options, suggesting some decline in familiarity with experimental logic. Younger respondents, while relatively accurate, exhibit slightly higher levels of uncertainty compared to middle-aged groups and have levels of reliance on medical authority comparable to 65+'s (16%).

Educational (table in next page) attainment emerges as the most significant differentiating factor. The proportion of respondents selecting the correct experimental design increases sharply with education, from 36,2% among those with low education to 61,4% among highly educated individuals. Conversely, reliance on less scientific approaches, such as subjective patient reports (13,3% vs. 6,1%) or medical authority (15,8% vs. 10,6%) and expressions of uncertainty (16,1% vs. 8,6%) decrease substantially with higher education. The gradient highlights the role of formal education in fostering understanding of scientific reasoning.

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Q8. [Scientific literacy] Imagine that some scientists are studying the effectiveness of a medicine for high blood pressure. I am going to present you with four options for conducting this study. Which of these options would be the most scientific way to establish the medicine's effectiveness?, By Education, 2026 (%)

	Low education n	Medium education n	High education n
Ask patients how they feel to see if they notice any effects	13,3%	8,6%	6,1%
Examine the effect of each component of the drug separately	18,6%	20,0%	12,3%
Administer the drug to some patients but not to others, and compare what happens to the two groups	36,2%	45,9%	61,4%
Rely solely on medical knowledge to determine the drug's efficacy	15,8%	10,7%	10,6%
Don't know	16,1%	14,8%	8,6%
I'd rather not answer	0,0%	0,0%	1,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Q8. [Scientific literacy] Imagine that some scientists are studying the effectiveness of a medicine for high blood pressure. I am going to present you with four options for conducting this study. Which of these options would be the most scientific way to establish the medicine's effectiveness?, By Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	1 - Far-Left	2	3	4 - Center	5	6	7 - Far-Right
Ask patients how they feel to see if they notice any effects	12,1%	10,8%	8,9%	9,2%	9,1%	7,4%	16,7%
Examine the effect of each component of the drug separately	12,1%	15,7%	14,9%	17,6%	17,5%	16,9%	19,4%
Administer the drug to some patients but not to others, and compare what happens to the two groups	27,3%	50,6%	51,6%	47,8%	48,6%	48,6%	40,3%
Rely solely on medical knowledge to determine the drug's efficacy	27,3%	7,2%	11,1%	12,0%	13,8%	14,2%	11,1%
Don't know	21,2%	15,7%	13,0%	13,5%	9,6%	12,8%	12,5%
I'd rather not answer	0,0%	0,0%	0,5%	0,0%	1,2%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Political orientation (tabled in the previous page) shows more nuanced variation. While the experimental design remains the most selected option across the spectrum, its prevalence is lower at the extremes, particularly among respondents on the far-left (27,3%) and somewhat reduced on the far-right (40,3%), compared to higher values among moderate positions (around 48–51%). Respondents on the far-left display relatively high reliance on both medical authority (27,3%) and uncertainty (21,2%), while those on the far-right show higher selection of less rigorous options such as subjective patient reports (16,7%). These patterns suggest that deviations from the most scientific reasoning are more pronounced at the ideological extremes, albeit in different ways.

6.3. Media literacy

Q9. *[Media literacy] I'm going to read out a few statements to you. Can you tell me, based on what you know, whether they are true or false?, 2026*

	True	False	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
RTP relies on advertising as its main source of funding.	38,0%	36,3%*	25,5%	0,1%
The news and content that a person sees on Instagram or Facebook are selected at random.	17,5%	57,0%*	25,3%	0,2%
Most of the media companies in Portugal are privately owned.	67,5%*	9,2%	23,2%	0,1%
Social media algorithms are primarily designed to show us posts on the topics that interest us most.	62,1%*	15,0%	22,8%	0,1%
In a digital newspaper, any text bearing an author's byline is an opinion piece.	38,4%	24,5%*	37,0%	0,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: (*) Correct answer.

To gauge media literacy levels, respondents were asked five questions in a true or false format, meaning that there was a correct answer. This aims to evaluate the knowledge respondents have about structural features of the Portuguese media ecosystem: Portugal's PSM RTP not depending on advertising for its operation, news on social media being curated, the majority of media companies being privately owned, the fact that algorithms personalise feeds and that not all texts on a news website that have a signature are opinion pieces.

The results reveal uneven levels of media literacy across different dimensions of knowledge about the media ecosystem. While some statements are correctly identified by a majority of respondents, others reveal substantial levels of misunderstanding and uncertainty. The highest levels of correct responses are observed in the statement that most media companies in Portugal are privately owned (67,5%) and that social media algorithms are designed to show users content aligned with their interests (62,1%).

Similarly, a majority correctly reject the idea that content on platforms such as Instagram or Facebook is selected at random (57,0%). However, knowledge is considerably weaker for other items: only 36,3% correctly identify that RTP does not rely primarily on advertising, and just 24,5% correctly reject the statement that any text with a byline in a digital newspaper is an opinion piece. Notably, levels of uncertainty remain high across several items, with “don’t know” responses reaching around one quarter or more of respondents in multiple cases (37,0% in the question of the byline in news texts).

Q9. [Media literacy] I'm going to read out a few statements to you. Can you tell me, based on what you know, whether they are true or false?, By Gender, 2026

	All	Men	Women
RTP relies on advertising as its main source of funding.			
True	38,0%	35,9%	40,3%
False	36,3%*	45,7%	27,6%
Don't know	25,5%	18,3%	32,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
The news and content that a person sees on Instagram or Facebook are selected at random.			
True	17,5%	18,4%	16,4%
False	57,0%*	59,4%	55,1%
Don't know	25,3%	21,9%	28,5%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,3%	0,1%
Most of the media companies in Portugal are privately owned.			
True	67,5%*	73,2%	62,4%
False	9,2%	11,6%	6,9%
Don't know	23,2%	15,1%	30,6%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
Social media algorithms are primarily designed to show us posts on the topics that interest us most.			
True	62,1%*	61,3%	63,4%
False	15,0%	19,9%	10,2%
Don't know	22,8%	18,6%	26,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
In a digital newspaper, any text bearing an author's byline is an opinion piece.			
True	38,4%	43,4%	34,0%
False	24,5%*	26,7%	22,2%
Don't know	37,0%	29,8%	43,6%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,2%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: (*) Correct answer.

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Gender differences are moderate but reveal some relevant contrasts. Men tend to provide more correct answers in certain items, particularly regarding RTP's funding model (45,7% correct against 27,6% among women) and the ownership structure of media companies (73,2% vs. 62,4%).

Women, in turn, show slightly higher correctness in understanding algorithmic curation (63,4% vs. 61,3%) but also display higher levels of uncertainty in several items, especially regarding authorship and opinion content (43,6% "don't know" vs. 29,8% among men). Overall, differences suggest greater confidence and accuracy among men in institutional knowledge, while women show more cautious response patterns.

Q9. [Media literacy] I'm going to read out a few statements to you. Can you tell me, based on what you know, whether they are true or false?, By Age, 2026

	All	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
RTP relies on advertising as its main source of funding.							
True	38,0%	42,1 %	34,4 %	35,0 %	39,1 %	45,6 %	31,1 %
False	36,3%*	32,2 %	30,7 %	37,9 %	39,2 %	38,2 %	35,2 %
Don't know	25,5%	25,0 %	34,7 %	27,0 %	21,7 %	16,2 %	33,7 %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
The news and content that a person sees on Instagram or Facebook are selected at random.							
True	17,5%	18,7 %	18,9 %	19,0 %	18,5 %	17,7 %	12,3 %
False	57,0%*	60,0 %	62,2 %	60,6 %	62,3 %	57,9 %	36,4 %
Don't know	25,3%	20,7 %	18,6 %	20,3 %	19,2 %	24,4 %	50,6 %
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,7%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,6%
Most of the media companies in Portugal are privately owned.							
True	67,5%*	52,0 %	59,0 %	68,2 %	74,5 %	77,8 %	58,5 %
False	9,2%	19,3 %	13,7 %	11,6 %	5,1%	6,5%	7,3%
Don't know	23,2%	28,0 %	27,0 %	20,3 %	20,4 %	15,7 %	34,2 %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
Social media algorithms are primarily designed to show us posts on the topics that interest us most.							
True	62,1%*	63,3 %	64,7 %	71,1 %	67,4 %	65,7 %	36,7 %
False	15,0%	18,0 %	16,1 %	14,1 %	15,8 %	14,2 %	13,3 %
Don't know	22,8%	18,0 %	18,9 %	14,8 %	16,8 %	20,1 %	50,0 %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
In a digital newspaper, any text bearing an author's byline is an opinion piece.							
True	38,4%	28,7 %	27,0 %	34,7 %	36,3 %	49,4 %	47,5 %
False	24,5%*	42,0 %	33,2 %	28,0 %	24,7 %	19,5 %	10,1 %
Don't know	37,0%	28,7 %	39,4 %	37,3 %	38,8 %	31,2 %	42,4 %

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I'd rather not answer 0,1% 0,7% 0,3% 0,0% 0,2% 0,0% 0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: (*) Correct answer.

Age differences are pronounced and reveal a non-linear pattern. Middle-aged groups (35–64) tend to display higher levels of correct responses across most items, particularly regarding media ownership (up to 77,8% among 55–64) and algorithmic curation (reaching 71,1% among 35–44). Younger respondents also perform relatively well on platform-related knowledge (e.g. 60,0% correctly rejecting randomness in content selection), but show weaker performance on institutional aspects such as RTP funding. Older respondents (65+) consistently exhibit lower levels of correct answers and substantially higher uncertainty, particularly striking in the case of algorithmic curation (50,0% “don’t know”) and content selection mechanisms, indicating a significant generational gap in media literacy.

Q9. [Media literacy] I'm going to read out a few statements to you. Can you tell me, based on what you know, whether they are true or false?, By Education, 2026

	All	Low education	Medium education	High education
RTP relies on advertising as its main source of funding.				
True	38,0%	33,4%	41,2%	38,7%
False	36,3% *	31,6%	36,2%	41,0%
Don't know	25,5%	34,7%	22,6%	20,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%
The news and content that a person sees on Instagram or Facebook are selected at random.				
True	17,5%	20,7%	19,2%	12,7%
False	57,0% *	36,5%	58,4%	74,9%
Don't know	25,3%	42,5%	22,4%	12,1%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,3%	0,0%	0,3%
Most of the media companies in Portugal are privately owned.				
True	67,5% *	55,8%	69,3%	76,7%
False	9,2%	11,4%	8,8%	7,6%
Don't know	23,2%	32,5%	21,9%	15,7%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%
Social media algorithms are primarily designed to show us posts on the topics that interest us most.				
True	62,1% *	43,0%	67,2%	74,9%
False	15,0%	13,7%	15,7%	15,3%
Don't know	22,8%	43,0%	17,2%	9,8%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%
In a digital newspaper, any text bearing an author's byline is an opinion piece.				
True	38,4%	36,6%	39,7%	38,4%

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False	24,5% *	16,8%	23,9%	32,5%
Don't know	37,0%	46,2%	36,3%	29,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,5%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: (*) Correct answer.

Educational attainment is the most consistent and powerful differentiating factor. Higher education is associated with significantly higher levels of correct responses across all items. For instance, 74,9% of highly educated respondents correctly reject the idea that social media content is random (compared to 36,5% among low education), and 76,7% correctly identify media ownership structures (against 55,8%). Similarly, understanding of algorithmic curation increases sharply with education (74,9% against 43,0%), while uncertainty decreases substantially. In contrast, respondents with lower levels of education display both lower accuracy and higher rates of “don't know,” particularly for more technical or structural aspects of the media system.

Q9. [Media literacy] I'm going to read out a few statements to you. Can you tell me, based on what you know, whether they are true or false?, By Political Orientation, 2026

	All	1 - Far-Left	2	3	4 - Center	5	6	7 - Far-Right
RTP relies on advertising as its main source of funding.								
True	38,0%	39,4% %	31,3% %	37,8% %	37,3% %	40,3% %	42,2% %	37,5% %
False	36,3% *	18,2% %	36,1% %	35,1% %	35,6% %	40,6% %	40,8% %	31,9% %
Don't know	25,5%	42,4% %	32,5% %	27,0% %	27,1% %	19,1% %	17,0% %	29,2% %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
The news and content that a person sees on Instagram or Facebook are selected at random.								
True	17,5%	25,0% %	12,0% %	14,8% %	18,8% %	17,1% %	15,0% %	30,6% %
False	57,0% *	31,3% %	53,0% %	58,5% %	54,7% %	64,4% %	60,5% %	47,2% %
Don't know	25,3%	43,8% %	34,9% %	26,7% %	26,3% %	18,6% %	24,5% %	20,8% %
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
Most of the media companies in Portugal are privately owned.								
True	67,5% *	40,6% %	69,9% %	68,2% %	66,1% %	74,5% %	70,7% %	58,3% %
False	9,2%	12,5% %	4,8% %	6,5% %	8,8% %	10,6% %	8,8% %	19,4% %
Don't know	23,2%	46,9% %	25,3% %	25,3% %	25,1% %	14,9% %	20,4% %	20,8% %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
Social media algorithms are primarily designed to show us posts on the topics that interest us most.								
True	62,1% *	40,6% %	48,2% %	56,1% %	63,7% %	67,8% %	69,4% %	63,0% %
False	15,0%	15,6% %	19,3% %	15,9% %	13,8% %	16,3% %	13,6% %	11,0% %

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Don't know	22,8%	43,8 %	32,5 %	28,0 %	22,4 %	15,8 %	17,0 %	24,7 %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
In a digital newspaper, any text bearing an author's byline is an opinion piece.								
True	38,4%	31,3 %	34,9 %	42,5 %	36,5 %	39,6 %	40,8 %	41,7 %
False	24,5% *	25,0 %	28,9 %	24,5 %	22,3 %	29,7 %	22,4 %	16,7 %
Don't know	37,0%	43,8 %	36,1 %	32,8 %	41,2 %	30,7 %	36,7 %	40,3 %
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: (*) Correct answer.

Political orientation reveals differentiated but less systematic patterns. Respondents positioned towards the centre and moderate right (positions 4–6) tend to display higher levels of correct responses across several items, particularly regarding media ownership and algorithmic curation. In contrast, those at the ideological extremes show more mixed patterns. Respondents on the far-left exhibit high levels of uncertainty (e.g. 46,9% “don’t know” for media ownership), while those on the far-right display lower accuracy in some items, such as the functioning of content selection on social media (47,2% correct vs. over 60,0% in several centrist groups). These results suggest that media literacy is somewhat lower at the ideological extremes, though in different ways, through uncertainty on the left and inaccuracies on the right.

6.4. News-finds me

In this section we explore the dynamics of the so-called *news-finds-me* perception (NFM), conceived and developed by Gil de Zuñiga et al. (2017). The authors define the perception as “the extent to which individuals believe they can indirectly stay informed about public affairs—despite not actively following the news—through general Internet use, information received from peers, and connections within online social networks. Thus, it captures people's perceptions that news will simply “find” them without seeking it.” (Gil de Zuñiga et al., 2017: 107).

While relevante at the media diet level, this perception is particularly useful in the framework of disinformation studies due to the underlying complexity of the trustworthiness dynamics when it comes to the selection or passive acceptance of information inflows, particularly regarding friends and acquaintances: “the reliance on friends-recommended contents might play a role in misinformation dissemination processes. NFM people who are reliant on peers to feed them with important news as they break, might be more likely to trust peer-generated contents, which does not necessarily correspond to verified factual professional news sources” (Gil de Zuñiga & Cheng, 2021: 8).

Q10. [News-finds-me] Next, please indicate whether your level of agreement with the following statements. Use a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree", 2026 (% and Means)

	I rely on my friends to tell me what's important when significant news stories break.	I can stay well-informed even when I don't actively follow the news.	I don't need to actively seek out news because, when important public issues arise, they reach me via social media.
1 - Strongly disagree	12,9%	8,9%	11,7%
2	17,6%	18,4%	16,4%
3 - Neither agree nor disagree	42,4%	38,3%	35,8%
4	21,9%	26,9%	27,5%
5 - Strongly agree	4,9%	7,1%	8,1%
Don't know	0,2%	0,3%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
	Means		
	2,88	3,05	3,04

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=I strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree.

The results indicate moderate levels of agreement with NFM attitudes, with mean values close to the midpoint of the scale across all statements. Among the three items, the belief that one can stay well-informed without actively following the news (mean=3.05) and that important public issues reach individuals via social media (3,04) show slightly higher agreement than reliance on friends to signal important news (2,88).

The distribution of responses reinforces this pattern: the largest share of respondents consistently selects the midpoint category ("neither agree nor disagree"), ranging from 35,8% to 42,4%, while levels of strong agreement remain relatively limited (between 4,9% and 8,1%). This suggests a general ambivalence towards passive news consumption, rather than strong endorsement.

At the sociodemographic level (table in the next page) and starting with gender, we find that differences are minimal and do not substantially alter the overall pattern. Women report slightly higher agreement with passive news exposure, particularly regarding the role of social media in delivering news (3,10 against 2,96 among men), while men show marginally higher reliance on interpersonal networks (2,90 vs. 2,86). These differences are small, indicating that NFM attitudes are broadly shared across genders.

Age differences reveal a clearer pattern. Younger respondents (17–34) display higher levels of agreement with passive news consumption, particularly in the belief that they can remain informed without actively following the news (3,24 and 3,22) and that news reaches them via social media (3,17 and 3,18). In contrast, older respondents (65+) show notably lower agreement with these statements (2,58 and 2,60, respectively), suggesting a stronger orientation towards active news seeking. Interestingly, reliance on friends slightly increases among older groups (3,03 among 65+), indicating a shift towards interpersonal rather than platform-mediated pathways. Lower social media rate usage among older individuals is also a factor in the age dynamics at hand (Cardoso et al., 2025).

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Q10. [News-finds-me] Next, please indicate whether your level of agreement with the following statements. Use a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree", By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (% and Means)

	I rely on my friends to tell me what's important when significant news stories break.	I can stay well-informed even when I don't actively follow the news.	I don't need to actively seek out news because, when important public issues arise, they reach me via social media.
All	2,88	3,05	3,04
Male	2,90	3,03	2,96
Female	2,86	3,06	3,10
17-24	2,85	3,24	3,17
25-34	2,98	3,22	3,18
35-44	2,79	3,14	3,21
45-54	2,77	3,22	3,10
55-64	2,92	2,91	3,01
65+	3,03	2,58	2,60
Low education	2,95	2,95	2,96
Medium education	2,90	3,14	3,14
High education	2,80	3,05	3,00
1 - Far-Left	2,83	3,04	2,67
2	3,04	2,63	2,60
3	2,86	2,86	2,79
4 - Center	2,92	3,10	3,12
5	2,81	3,10	3,07
6	2,80	3,08	3,20
7 - Far-Right	2,94	3,42	3,54

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: a) Scale 1 to 5 where 1=strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree.

Educational differences are relatively limited but show some differentiation. Respondents with medium education report slightly higher agreement with passive news consumption (3,14 for both statements related to passive exposure), while those with higher education display somewhat lower agreement (around 3,00 / 3,05), suggesting a marginally greater tendency towards active information seeking. Individuals with lower education show slightly higher reliance on interpersonal networks (2,95), though differences remain modest overall.

Political orientation reveals more pronounced variation, particularly at the fringes. Respondents on the far-right exhibit the highest levels of agreement with passive news consumption, especially regarding staying informed without actively following the news

(3,42) and the role of social media in delivering information (3,54), representing the highest values observed in the dataset. In contrast, respondents on the far-left and centre display more moderate levels of agreement, while those at position 2 show notably lower agreement (e.g. 2,63 and 2,60), indicating greater scepticism towards passive news exposure. These patterns suggest that NFM attitudes are more prevalent among individuals positioned towards the right of the ideological spectrum.

Overall, the findings point to a moderate and widely distributed endorsement of passive news consumption, characterised by ambivalence rather than strong agreement. Age and political orientation emerge as the most relevant differentiating factors, while gender and education play a more limited role in structuring these attitudes.

7. Perceptions on disinformation in day-to-day life

7.1. Coming to contact with disinformation

Q11. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received any information or news that you think might be false regarding..., 2026 (%)

	Yes	No	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
...nutrition and well-being?	39,8%	60,0%	0,2%	0,1%
...vaccines?	23,8%	75,9%	0,3%	0,1%
...the cause of the major summer wildfires?	19,0%	80,8%	0,1%	0,1%
...climate change?	36,6%	63,2%	0,1%	0,1%
...alternative therapies?	26,1%	73,7%	0,2%	0,1%
...medical treatments?	29,9%	69,9%	0,1%	0,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Regarding the potential contact with disinformation, respondents were asked if they feel they might have received potentially false information regarding a wide array of topics. The results are affirmative, with users having indeed received such content but they vary substantially across topics.

Overall, the highest levels of perceived exposure to potential disinformation are found in nutrition and well-being (39,8%) and climate change (36,6%), followed by medical treatments (29,9%) and alternative therapies (26,1%). In contrast, lower levels are reported for vaccines (23,8%) and particularly for the causes of major summer wildfires (19,0%). This does not mean that there is necessarily less disinformation circulating in regards to the less frequently mentioned topics but that some topics are more associated with perceived disinformation than others, regardless of the volume of content in circulation.

Q11. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received any information or news that you think might be false regarding... By Gender, 2026 (%)

	All	Men	Women
...nutrition and well-being?			
Yes	39,8%	39,4%	39,9%
No	60,0%	60,3%	59,9%
Don't know	0,2%	0,3%	0,1%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%
...vaccines?			
Yes	23,8%	26,2%	21,3%
No	75,9%	73,3%	78,4%
Don't know	0,3%	0,4%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%
...the cause of the major summer wildfires?			
Yes	19,0%	22,2%	15,7%
No	80,8%	77,6%	84,0%
Don't know	0,1%	0,2%	0,1%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,2%
...climate change?			
Yes	36,6%	40,1%	33,1%
No	63,2%	59,6%	66,8%
Don't know	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%
...alternative therapies?			
Yes	26,1%	26,6%	25,2%
No	73,7%	73,1%	74,5%
Don't know	0,2%	0,3%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%
...medical treatments?			
Yes	29,9%	29,9%	30,1%
No	69,9%	70,0%	69,8%
Don't know	0,1%	0,1%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Gender differences are minimal across most topics. Men report slightly higher exposure to suspected false information regarding vaccines (26,2% against 21,3%), climate change (40,1% vs. 33,1%), and wildfires (22,2% vs. 15,7%), while women report marginally higher exposure in nutrition and medical treatments. However, these variations remain limited, indicating broadly similar perceptions across genders.

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Q11. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received any information or news that you think might be false regarding... By Age, 2026 (%)

	All	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
...nutrition and well-being?							
Yes	39,8%	55,3 %	47,4 %	40,6 %	41,3 %	38,6 %	22,5 %
No	60,0%	44,0 %	52,3 %	59,4 %	58,7 %	61,2 %	76,8 %
Don't know	0,2%	0,0%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,6%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
...vaccines?							
Yes	23,8%	32,7 %	30,4 %	28,7 %	24,5 %	19,7 %	11,7 %
No	75,9%	65,3 %	69,3 %	71,3 %	75,5 %	80,0 %	87,6 %
Don't know	0,3%	1,3%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,6%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
...the cause of the major summer wildfires?							
Yes	19,0%	32,5 %	23,0 %	23,5 %	17,4 %	17,2 %	9,2%
No	80,8%	66,2 %	77,0 %	76,2 %	82,6 %	82,6 %	90,5 %
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,0%	0,2%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	1,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
...climate change?							
Yes	36,6%	44,7 %	44,6 %	44,4 %	38,7 %	31,3 %	20,0 %
No	63,2%	54,7 %	55,4 %	55,6 %	61,1 %	68,4 %	79,7 %
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,2%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
...alternative therapies?							
Yes	26,1%	39,7 %	28,9 %	29,9 %	26,7 %	23,4 %	15,2 %
No	73,7%	58,9 %	70,8 %	69,8 %	73,3 %	76,4 %	84,5 %
Don't know	0,2%	0,7%	0,3%	0,3%	0,0%	0,2%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
...medical treatments?							
Yes	29,9%	43,7 %	33,1 %	36,7 %	30,2 %	28,4 %	15,2 %
No	69,9%	55,6 %	66,9 %	63,3 %	69,8 %	71,6 %	84,4 %
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Age differences are considerably more pronounced. Younger respondents (17–34) consistently report higher exposure to suspected disinformation across all topics. For example, 55,3% of those aged 17–24 report encountering potentially false information about nutrition and well-being, compared to only 22,5% among those aged 65+.

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Similarly, perceived exposure to disinformation on climate change declines sharply with age (44,7% among 17–24 against 20,0% among 65+). This pattern is consistent across all domains, indicating that younger individuals are either more exposed to, or more likely to recognise, questionable information. Portugal stands out among european countries in regards to concerns about the truthfulness of online content with 7 out of 10 respondents of the Digital News Report declaring to be concerned (71,0%). The proportion is slightly higher among 65+'s than among the 18-24's (75,0% against 69,0%), a trend that is not visible in the global sample with concern rates being flat across all age groups (Cardoso et al., 2025, Newman et al., 2025).

Q11. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received any information or news that you think might be false regarding... By Education, 2026 (%)

	All	Low education	Medium education	High education
		n	n	n
...nutrition and well-being?				
Yes	39,8%	28,0%	43,3%	47,2%
No	60,0%	71,9%	56,3%	52,6%
Don't know	0,2%	0,0%	0,4%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
...vaccines?				
Yes	23,8%	20,9%	24,9%	25,6%
No	75,9%	78,7%	74,8%	74,1%
Don't know	0,3%	0,3%	0,3%	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
...the cause of the major summer wildfires?				
Yes	19,0%	19,8%	20,4%	16,8%
No	80,8%	79,6%	79,6%	83,1%
Don't know	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%
...climate change?				
Yes	36,6%	31,8%	39,1%	38,5%
No	63,2%	67,8%	60,8%	61,5%
Don't know	0,1%	0,3%	0,1%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
...alternative therapies?				
Yes	26,1%	21,0%	28,4%	28,3%
No	73,7%	78,5%	71,3%	71,6%
Don't know	0,2%	0,3%	0,3%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
...medical treatments?				
Yes	29,9%	26,1%	31,0%	32,5%
No	69,9%	73,8%	68,8%	67,5%
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Educational differences also show a clear gradient. Respondents with higher education levels report greater exposure to suspected disinformation, particularly in nutrition (47,2% vs. 28,0% among low education) and medical treatments (32,5% against 26,1%). This may reflect higher levels of critical awareness or greater engagement with information-rich environments. Conversely, individuals with lower education are more likely to report not encountering such information.

Q11. Thinking back over the last 7 days, have you received any information or news that you think might be false regarding... By Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	All	1 - Far-Left	2	3	4 - Center	5	6	7 - Far-Right
...nutrition and well-being?								
Yes	39,8%	32,3%	32,5%	35,0%	39,2%	44,2%	43,5%	44,4%
No	60,0%	67,7%	67,5%	65,0%	60,8%	55,1%	56,5%	54,2%
Don't know	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,7%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
...vaccines?								
Yes	23,8%	34,4%	21,7%	20,8%	21,7%	26,2%	23,1%	42,5%
No	75,9%	65,6%	78,3%	79,0%	78,2%	73,3%	76,2%	56,2%
Don't know	0,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,1%	0,5%	0,7%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
...the cause of the major summer wildfires?								
Yes	19,0%	25,0%	16,7%	16,7%	18,4%	19,6%	18,4%	33,3%
No	80,8%	75,0%	83,3%	83,0%	81,4%	80,2%	81,6%	65,3%
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,3%	0,1%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
...climate change?								
Yes	36,6%	40,6%	31,3%	28,6%	35,4%	38,6%	48,0%	58,3%
No	63,2%	59,4%	68,7%	71,4%	64,4%	61,1%	51,4%	40,3%
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,2%	0,7%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
...alternative therapies?								
Yes	26,1%	25,0%	26,5%	23,7%	24,1%	28,2%	26,4%	38,9%
No	73,7%	75,0%	73,5%	76,3%	75,8%	71,3%	73,0%	58,3%
Don't know	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,1%	0,5%	0,7%	1,4%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%
...medical treatments?								
Yes	29,9%	37,5%	25,3%	23,5%	29,6%	31,4%	35,4%	41,7%
No	69,9%	62,5%	74,7%	76,5%	70,4%	68,3%	64,6%	56,9%
Don't know	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Political orientation reveals some of the most striking differences. Respondents on the far-right consistently report higher exposure to suspected disinformation across all topics. For instance, 58,3% report encountering potentially false information on climate change, compared to 28,6%–40,6% across left and centre groups. Similar patterns emerge for vaccines (42,5% on the far-right vs. around 21% to 26% in most other groups) and medical treatments (41,7% against approximately 23% to 35%). This suggests that individuals at the right end of the ideological spectrum are either more exposed to, or more likely to perceive, misinformation across multiple domains.

The perception of having encountered disinformation is widespread but unevenly distributed. Topic salience, age, education, and particularly political orientation play key roles in shaping these perceptions, while gender differences remain comparatively marginal.

Q12. And regarding the information you received that you think might be false, through which channels did you receive it?, 2026 (%)

	Yes	No	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
Face-to-face or telephone conversations	40,6%	58,8%	0,5%	0,1%
Instant messaging apps (WhatsApp, Telegram...)	49,8%	49,8%	0,4%	0,0%
Social media (Facebook, X, Bluesky...)	74,3%	25,3%	0,4%	0,0%
Online video-based social media (YouTube, Instagram, Twitch, TikTok...)[MP1]	68,1%	30,9%	0,9%	0,1%
Digital or print media	39,9%	59,8%	0,4%	0,0%
Television or online TV platforms (Netflix, HBO Max, Prime Video, Disney+, Apple TV, Sky, Filmin, etc.)	36,7%	62,7%	0,6%	0,1%
Radio or podcasts	31,2%	68,3%	0,5%	0,1%
Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT, Google summaries, Gemini...)	38,2%	61,2%	0,6%	0,0%
Others	24,7%	69,2%	5,1%	1,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=1185 (Those who received information or news in the last week which they think might be false).

Considering the channels in which people suspect they might have received disinformation content in the week prior results show that suspected disinformation is overwhelmingly perceived as circulating through digital and networked channels, with social media clearly standing out as the primary gateway.

Overall, 74.3% of respondents who reported encountering potentially false information identify social media as a source, followed by online video-based platforms (68,1%) and instant messaging apps (49,8%). More traditional channels such as television (36,7%), radio (31,2%), and print / digital news media (39,9%) are less frequently associated with suspected disinformation, though still relevant.

Results fall in line with previous findings which indicated that people believe that misinformation is mainly found on social media (Newman et al., 2020) and network environments are less reliable and more prone to the circulation of disinformation (Fletcher

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& Nielsen, 2019, Kalogeropoulos et al., 2019). This also impacts the perception of news content in network environments. Data for Portugal identifies a clear pattern when it comes to trust: news in social media are considered substantially less trustworthy than news in general and news found on search engines (Cardoso et al., 2025). These systematic findings are illustrative of the erosion of trust in broader information environments due to disinformation awareness (Lewandowsky et al., 2023).

Q12. And regarding the information you received that you think might be false, through which channels did you receive it?, By Gender, 2026 (%)

	All	Men	Women
Face-to-face or telephone conversations	40,6%	42,6%	38,2%
Instant messaging apps	49,8%	53,9%	45,4%
Social media	74,3%	74,2%	74,6%
Online video-based social media	68,1%	68,8%	67,3%
Digital or print media	39,9%	43,1%	36,0%
Television or online TV platforms	36,7%	39,8%	32,7%
Radio or podcasts	31,2%	34,2%	27,6%
Artificial Intelligence	38,2%	40,3%	35,9%
Others	24,7%	27,9%	21,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=1185 (Those who received information or news in the last week which they think might be false). For complete description of categories with examples see Q12 general table.

Gender differences remain limited overall. Men report somewhat higher exposure through instant messaging apps (53,9%), digital / print media, and AI tools (40,3%), while women show marginally higher exposure through social media (74,6%). However, these differences are relatively small and do not substantially alter the overall pattern.

Q12. And regarding the information you received that you think might be false, through which channels did you receive it?, By Age, 2026 (%)

	All	17-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Face-to-face or telephone conversations	40,6 %	51,4%	48,2%	37,2%	30,8%	40,0%	50,5%
Instant messaging apps	49,8 %	54,1%	52,3%	45,9%	40,4%	58,3%	56,2%
Social media	74,3 %	71,4%	69,5%	74,5%	79,2%	75,3%	70,5%
Online video-based social media	68,1 %	67,9%	69,5%	71,4%	71,3%	62,6%	61,9%
Digital or print media	39,9 %	49,1%	40,3%	39,8%	40,7%	36,6%	34,3%
Television or online TV platforms	36,7 %	45,0%	38,6%	37,2%	36,9%	32,3%	31,4%
Radio or podcasts	31,2 %	42,3%	30,9%	35,7%	29,3%	27,7%	23,8%
Artificial Intelligence	38,2 %	50,5%	47,7%	37,8%	34,7%	30,3%	34,3%
Others	24,7 %	35,7%	25,0%	26,4%	22,4%	23,4%	17,9%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=1185 (Those who received information or news in the last week which they think might be false). For complete description of categories with examples see Q12 general table.

Age differences are particularly pronounced. Younger respondents (17–34) report significantly higher exposure through instant messaging apps (over 50,0%), AI tools (up to 50,5%), and face-to-face conversations, indicating a more hybrid information environment combining digital and interpersonal exchanges. In contrast, older groups (55+) report lower exposure through digital-native channels such as AI and video platforms, but relatively higher reliance on messaging apps and interpersonal communication. Notably, the use of AI as a perceived gateway declines steadily with age.

Q12. And regarding the information you received that you think might be false, through which channels did you receive it?, By Education, 2026 (%)

	All	Low education	Medium education	High education
Face-to-face or telephone conversations	40,6%	41,4%	40,6%	40,0%
Instant messaging apps	49,8%	51,5%	53,2%	45,2%
Social media	74,3%	73,6%	71,6%	77,5%
Online video-based social media	68,1%	66,4%	66,9%	70,5%
Digital or print media	39,9%	42,7%	42,9%	34,8%
Television or online TV platforms	36,7%	46,1%	35,8%	31,4%
Radio or podcasts	31,2%	37,6%	31,5%	26,4%
Artificial Intelligence	38,2%	41,7%	40,8%	33,2%
Others	24,7%	32,1%	25,1%	19,5%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=1185 (Those who received information or news in the last week which they think might be false). For complete description of categories with examples see Q12 general table.

Educational differences are moderate. Individuals with lower education levels report slightly higher exposure through television (46,1%), radio (37,6%), and “other” sources (32,1%), while those with higher education show greater association with social media (77,5%) and online video platforms (70,5%). This suggests that more educated respondents are more embedded in digital information ecosystems where disinformation is perceived to circulate.

Q12. And regarding the information you received that you think might be false, through which channels did you receive it?, By Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	All	1 - Far-Left	2	3	4 - Center	5	6	7 - Far-Right
Face-to-face or telephone conversations	40,6 %	47,1%	32,6%	49,7%	38,7%	38,1%	34,4%	46,3%
Instant messaging apps	49,8 %	72,2%	39,5%	52,4%	49,5%	50,8%	46,9%	52,8%
Social media	74,3 %	61,1%	83,7%	73,7%	75,1%	75,4%	72,9%	67,9%

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Online video-based social media	68,1 %	66,7%	60,5%	70,1%	66,9%	66,3%	75,0%	75,5%
Digital or print media	39,9 %	55,6%	27,9%	39,0%	37,8%	39,9%	49,0%	52,8%
Television or online TV platforms	36,7 %	35,3%	27,9%	33,3%	34,4%	38,9%	42,7%	56,6%
Radio or podcasts	31,2 %	35,3%	23,3%	26,2%	27,6%	35,3%	31,3%	54,7%
Artificial Intelligence	38,2 %	50,0%	25,6%	35,3%	36,8%	39,5%	43,8%	49,1%
Others	24,7 %	29,4%	23,3%	25,8%	23,3%	24,1%	23,7%	28,3%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=1185 (Those who received information or news in the last week which they think might be false). For complete description of categories with examples see Q12 general table.

Political orientation reveals more substantial variation. Respondents on the far-right consistently report higher exposure across most channels, particularly television (56,6%), radio/podcasts (54,7%), digital/print media (52,8%), and AI (49,1%), suggesting a broader attribution of disinformation across both traditional and digital ecosystems. At the same time, social media remains the dominant channel across all ideological groups, peaking among respondents at position “2” (83,7%). Interestingly, respondents on the far-left report the highest exposure to instant messaging apps (72,2%) and AI (50,0%), indicating different channel configurations across ideological extremes.

Considering the sociodemographic landscape, the perception of disinformation gateways is strongly shaped by digital platforms, especially social media and video-based environments, while interpersonal communication and messaging apps also play a central role. Demographic differences highlight that younger, more educated, and politically extreme groups tend to perceive a broader and more digitally mediated ecosystem of disinformation circulation.

7.2. Sharing disinformation

Q13. In the last 7 days, have you shared any information or news that you think might be false..., 2026 (%)

	Yes	No	Don't use SM	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
Q13.1. ...on your social media or messaging apps?	11,9%	82,9%	5,2%	0,0%	0,0%
Q13.2. ...in face-to-face or telephone conversations with other people?	13,1%	86,9%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Considering the self-reported sharing of information believed to be false results point to a limited though not negligible practice. Overall, 11,9% of respondents report having shared such content via social media or messaging apps, while a slightly higher proportion (13,1%) report doing so in face-to-face or telephone conversations.

This suggests that interpersonal communication remains at least as important as digital environments in the potential dissemination of misinformation, even if exposure is primarily digital.

Demographic differences (table in the next page) reveal important patterns. Men are consistently more likely to report sharing potentially false information than women, both online (14,1% against 9,6%) and offline (15,4% against 10,6%). Age is one of the strongest differentiators: younger respondents (17–24) stand out with the highest levels of self-reported sharing (21,3% online and 23,8% offline), with a general decline across older age groups, although some fluctuation appears among middle-aged respondents.

Educational differences are present but modest. Individuals with lower education levels report slightly higher sharing rates, particularly in interpersonal contexts (15,2%), while those with higher education report lower levels overall, especially offline (10,6%). This suggests a weak but consistent association between education and reduced engagement in the sharing of questionable information.

Q13. In the last 7 days, have you shared any information or news that you think might be false..., By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (%) [Proportion who have shared]

	Q13.1. ...on your social media or messaging apps?	Q13.2. ...in face-to-face or telephone conversations with other people?
All	11,9%	13,1%
Male	14,1%	15,4%
Female	9,6%	10,6%
17-24	21,3%	23,8%
25-34	14,9%	17,6%
35-44	10,6%	12,2%
45-54	7,0%	7,4%
55-64	15,0%	14,2%
65+	9,8%	12,3%
Low education	12,7%	15,2%
Medium education	12,1%	13,5%
High education	10,9%	10,6%
1 - Far-Left	15,2%	15,6%
2	7,2%	6,0%
3	9,2%	12,7%
4 - Center	10,4%	12,0%
5	13,8%	12,9%
6	17,6%	16,3%
7 - Far-Right	20,5%	23,6%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: %'s correspond to proportion of people who have replied "yes" when asked if they shared information they think might be false in the previous week.

Political orientation shows a more pronounced gradient. Respondents at the political fringes report higher levels of sharing, with the far-right displaying the highest levels overall (20,5% online and 23,6% offline), followed by the far-left (around 15,0%). Intermediate ideological positions, particularly those closer to the center, report lower levels. This pattern suggests that stronger ideological identification, regardless of direction, may be associated with a greater likelihood of sharing information perceived as potentially false.

In sum, while the majority of respondents do not report sharing disinformation, a non-negligible minority, particularly younger individuals and those at ideological extremes, acknowledge having done so, with interpersonal communication playing a surprisingly prominent role alongside digital platforms. Most importantly, the fact that these figures are based on self-perception ("information you think might be false") introduces an additional layer of interpretation. As such, they tend to reflect a more complex attitudinal framework, comprising behavior, awareness, reflexivity and uncertainty about information and source accuracy and trustworthiness.

7.3. The vulnerability to disinformation

Q14. Confidence in identifying disinformation, 2026 (% and Means)

	%	
	Q14.1 How confident are you that you can identify information that is false or distorts reality: very confident, fairly confident, not very confident or not at all confident?	Q14.2 To what extent are you confident that the average person in Portugal can distinguish information that is false?
1 - Very confident	12,5%	4,5%
2 - Fairly confident	58,5%	31,2%
3 - Not very confident	22,7%	45,4%
4 - Not at all confident	5,4%	17,1%
Don't know	0,6%	1,8%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,0%
	Means	
Mean	2,21	2,77

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

When enquired about their capacity and the capacity of others to identify disinformation, the findings reveal a notable asymmetry between self-perceived ability and perceptions of others' abilities to identify disinformation. At the aggregate level, respondents express moderate confidence in their own capacity to recognize false or misleading information (mean= 2,21 on a 1–4 scale, where lower values indicate higher confidence). A large

majority report being either “fairly confident” (58,5%) or “very confident” (12,5%), with only a minority expressing low confidence.

In contrast, confidence in the average person’s ability is substantially lower (mean=2.77). Here, perceptions shift markedly toward skepticism: 45,4% consider the average person “not very confident”, and 17,1% “not at all confident” in distinguishing false information.

Demographic patterns provide further nuance (table in the next page). Women report slightly higher confidence than men in both self-assessment and evaluation of others. Age differences are particularly pronounced: older respondents (especially 65+) express the highest confidence in their own abilities, while younger groups report lower confidence. At the same time, confidence in others also increases with age, though it remains consistently lower than self-assessments across all groups.

Q14. Confidence in identifying disinformation, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Q14.1 How confident are you that you can identify information that is false or distorts reality: very confident, fairly confident, not very confident or not at all confident?	Q14.2 To what extent are you confident that the average person in Portugal can distinguish information that is false?
All	2,21	2,77
Male	2,12	2,71
Femaie	2,29	2,82
17-24	2,00	2,58
25-34	2,14	2,65
35-44	2,09	2,68
45-54	2,22	2,77
55-64	2,26	2,87
65+	2,43	2,93
Low education	2,36	2,70
Medium education	2,20	2,74
High education	2,08	2,84
1 - Far-Left	2,34	2,58
2	2,27	3,18
3	2,20	2,81
4 - Center	2,25	2,74
5	2,14	2,74
6	2,22	2,82
7 - Far-Right	2,00	2,49

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1-Very confident to 4-Not confident at all.

Education presents a more complex picture. Individuals with lower education levels report higher confidence in their own ability, whereas those with higher education express comparatively lower self-confidence but greater confidence in others. This may reflect differences in epistemic caution or awareness of information complexity.

Political orientation reveals a clear gradient. Respondents at the far-right report the lowest confidence in their own ability (mean=2,00, indicating higher confidence numerically but actually lower confidence given the scale direction) and also the lowest confidence in others (2,49), while those closer to the center or moderate positions tend to express more balanced evaluations. (Note: since lower values indicate higher confidence, far-right respondents appear more confident in themselves numerically but also exhibit relatively low trust in others.)

The gap identified in the judgement of personal capacity and if the capacity of others suggests a clear “third-person effect”, where individuals perceive themselves as more capable than others in navigating misinformation. This effect has been widely covered in literature. At the foundational level, Davison (1983) identified a pattern of self-immunity, where people perceive media messages as having greater effects on others than on themselves.

More recently, and referring specifically to disinformation, Nielsen & Graves (2017) describe patterns of overestimated self-resistance to fake news in parallel to the underestimation of the resistance of others, who are more likely to be exposed to and influenced by disinformation. Corbu et al., (2020) establish through comparative analysis that this perceptive framework applies in the european context and, more recently the effect has been identified in regards to health disinformation and to the Covid-19 pandemic specifically (Chen & Fu, 2022, Wei et al., 2021, Yang & Tian, 2021). Importantly, the effect of this perception frameworks should not be ignored when it comes to the satisfaction with democratic systems as a whole, an important point raised by Nisbet et al., (2021) when concluding that the presumed influence of election disinformation on others reduces a person’s own satisfaction with democracy.

7.4. AI and disinformation

Q15. [AI] Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements:, 2026 (% and Means)

	%	
	Q15.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) makes it easier, faster and cheaper to spread fake news.	P15.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a useful tool that helps people debunk rumours or lies that spread as true news.
1- Strongly disagree	5,5%	11,3%
2	4,3%	8,0%
3	8,1%	12,9%
4	21,6%	27,9%
5	17,8%	17,8%
6	13,4%	8,3%
7 - Strongly agree	21,6%	6,5%
Don't know	7,1%	6,8%

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I'd rather not answer	0,5%	0,6%
	Means	
Mean	4,83	3,90

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Considering the role of AI in disinformation, both as a threat and as an opportunity, the results point to a clear but nuanced dual perception of technology in the context of disinformation. On the one hand, respondents broadly agree that AI facilitates the spread of fake news, with a relatively high mean score (4,83 on a 1–7 scale). On the other, they express more moderate agreement that AI can help debunk false information (3,90), indicating a more cautious or uncertain evaluation of its positive role. The percentage distribution across the scale reinforces this asymmetry. Agreement that AI enables the spread of disinformation is relatively strong and polarized toward higher values, with 21,6% “strongly agreeing”. In contrast, perceptions of AI as a corrective tool are more concentrated in mid-scale responses, with fewer strong endorsements (only 6,5% “strongly agree”), suggesting that its mitigating potential is less firmly established in public opinion.

Q15. [AI] Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements:, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Q15.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) makes it easier, faster and cheaper to spread fake news.	P15.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a useful tool that helps people debunk rumours or lies that spread as true news.
All	4,83	3,90
Male	4,88	4,03
Femaie	4,79	3,79
17-24	4,52	4,05
25-34	4,76	3,92
35-44	4,72	3,83
45-54	5,00	3,83
55-64	4,84	4,03
65+	4,89	3,83
Low education	4,58	3,91
Medium education	4,87	3,87
High education	4,98	3,94
1 - Far-Left	4,11	3,46
2	4,90	3,24
3	5,00	3,73
4 - Center	4,79	3,85
5	4,92	4,19

6	4,74	4,06
7 - Far-Right	4,63	4,32

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1-Strongly disagree and 7-Strongly agree.

Demographic differences provide additional granularity. Men express slightly higher agreement than women on both dimensions, particularly regarding AI's usefulness in debunking. Age patterns show that middle-aged groups (especially 45–54) are most convinced of AI's role in spreading fake news, while younger respondents (17–24) are comparatively less concerned but more open to AI's corrective potential (4,05), as are 55–64's (4,03).

Education introduces a subtle but consistent gradient. Higher-educated respondents are more likely to agree that AI facilitates disinformation (4,98), while differences regarding its debunking role are smaller, suggesting that greater awareness of technological capabilities may increase sensitivity to risks without substantially boosting optimism about solutions.

Political orientation reveals one of the most distinctive patterns. While concern about AI enabling fake news is relatively widespread across the spectrum, respondents at the far-left report lower agreement (4,11) compared to other groups. In contrast, confidence in AI as a debunking tool increases toward the right, peaking among the far-right (4,32). This suggests that attitudes toward AI's role are not only technological but also ideologically mediated, particularly regarding its perceived benefits.

The findings highlight a context of cautious ambivalence: AI is widely recognized as a powerful enabler of disinformation, while its capacity to counteract it is acknowledged but less strongly trusted. This imbalance suggests that public perceptions are shaped more by concerns about scale, speed, and manipulation than by confidence in technological solutions, reinforcing the importance of governance, transparency, and complementary human-led interventions. Portuguese respondents then reflect a well covered perception pattern in which AI is increasingly framed as both a driver of and a response to disinformation, simultaneously enabling the large-scale production of misleading content while supporting fact-checking, detection, and verification practices (Qian et al., 2024, OECD, 2024, Samet, 2025).

8. Attitudes on disinformation and science

8.1. Impact of disinformation

Q16. [Impacts of disinformation] To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Please use a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 is 'strongly disagree' and 7 is 'strongly agree', 2026 (% and Means)

	%			
	P16.1 The circulation of disinformation or rumours can have harmful effects on public health.	P16.2 Misinformation and rumours have the power to manipulate people's beliefs.	P16.3 Misinformation and rumours cause people to distrust institutions.	P16.4 Misinformation and rumours pose a threat to democracy.
1- Strongly disagree	2,5%	3,0%	2,8%	3,9%
2	4,2%	2,8%	3,4%	4,6%
3	7,7%	6,1%	6,1%	9,1%
4	18,7%	16,8%	17,0%	18,0%
5	20,4%	18,0%	19,4%	18,6%
6	15,2%	17,6%	17,7%	15,5%
7 - Strongly agree	30,1%	35,2%	32,8%	29,2%
Don't know	1,2%	0,4%	0,8%	1,1%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
	Means			
Mean	5,19	5,39	5,33	5,09

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Gauging the wider societal impacts of disinformation, the findings show a strong and consistent consensus that disinformation has significant societal impacts, with high levels of agreement across all four dimensions measured. All mean scores are above 5 on a 1–7 scale, indicating that respondents broadly perceive misinformation and rumours as harmful, influential, and structurally consequential.

Among the different impacts, the strongest agreement is found in the perception that disinformation has the power to manipulate people's beliefs (mean=5,39), followed closely by the view that it causes distrust in institutions (5,33). These results suggest that respondents are particularly sensitive to the cognitive and institutional consequences of disinformation. Slightly lower, though still high, are perceptions of its harmful effects on public health (5,19) and its role as a threat to democracy (5,09), indicating that while these structural impacts are widely acknowledged, they may be perceived as somewhat less immediate or direct. The distribution of responses reinforces this pattern, with a large proportion of respondents selecting higher agreement categories, including over 30% "strongly agreeing" that misinformation manipulates beliefs and causes distrust. Disagreement levels are minimal across all items, pointing to a broad societal consensus on the seriousness of the issue.

Q16. [Impacts of disinformation] To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Please use a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 is 'strongly disagree' and 7 is 'strongly agree', By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	P16.1 The circulation of misinformation or rumours can have harmful effects on public health.	P16.2 Misinformation and rumours have the power to manipulate people's beliefs.	P16.3 Misinformation and rumours cause people to distrust institutions.	P16.4 Misinformation and rumours pose a threat to democracy.
All	5,19	5,39	5,33	5,09
Male	5,10	5,38	5,29	5,08
Femaie	5,29	5,41	5,38	5,10
17-24	5,03	5,11	4,91	4,85
25-34	5,04	5,15	4,97	4,91
35-44	5,27	5,52	5,42	5,17
45-54	5,50	5,64	5,59	5,33
55-64	5,40	5,63	5,65	5,31
65+	4,54	4,90	4,95	4,57
Low education	4,76	4,97	4,95	4,72
Medium education	5,26	5,40	5,35	5,07
High education	5,54	5,78	5,67	5,46
1 - Far-Left	4,38	4,45	4,45	4,68
2	5,61	5,67	5,59	5,49
3	5,20	5,49	5,35	5,25
4 - Center	5,23	5,39	5,36	5,10
5	5,19	5,41	5,34	5,02
6	5,08	5,44	5,26	4,86
7 - Far-Right	4,98	4,96	5,22	4,81

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges between 1-Strongly disagree and 7-Strongly agree.

Demographic differences are present but do not fundamentally alter the overarching consensus. Women consistently report slightly higher levels of agreement than men, suggesting greater sensitivity to the impacts of disinformation. Age patterns indicate that middle-aged groups (45–64) express the highest concern, particularly regarding manipulation and distrust, while younger (17–24) and older (65+) respondents show comparatively lower levels of agreement, though still above the midpoint.

Education reveals a clear gradient: higher-educated respondents consistently perceive stronger impacts, especially regarding manipulation (5,78) and institutional distrust (5,67). This may reflect greater awareness of systemic and long-term consequences.

Political orientation introduces more variation. Respondents at the far-left report the lowest levels of agreement across all dimensions, while those in intermediate positions (particularly category 2) express the highest concern. The far-right also reports slightly lower levels of perceived impact compared to the center, especially regarding threats to democracy (4,81). This suggests that perceptions of disinformation's consequences are partially shaped by ideological positioning, particularly in relation to institutional trust and democratic concerns.

Overall, the results indicate a high level of societal awareness of the risks posed by disinformation, especially regarding its capacity to shape beliefs and erode trust. At the same time, demographic and ideological variations point to differences in how these risks are interpreted and prioritised, which may have implications for policy communication and intervention strategies.

The concern about impact of disinformation is well expressed by citizens across a wide range of sources, the general consensus being that this impact tends to be systemic (Lewandowsky et al., 2023) and in need of institutional strengthening (Altay, 2026).

8.2. Disinformation and freedom of press

Q17. [Press freedom] Please indicate which of these two statements you agree with most; 2026 (%)

	%
The government should take measures to restrict false information online, even if this limits press freedom.	65,5%
Press freedom must be protected, even if false information is published.	31,4%
Don't know	3,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

When confronted with the balance between government intervention to mitigate and combat disinformation and the impact of press freedom, the results reveal a strong preference among respondents for government intervention to restrict false information online, even at the potential cost of limiting press freedom. A clear majority (65,5%) support this position, compared to 31,4% who prioritise protecting press freedom even if false information is published. This indicates that, in the current informational environment, concerns about disinformation outweigh classical liberal norms of unrestricted press freedom for a substantial portion of the population.

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Q17. [Press freedom] Please indicate which of these two statements you agree with most:
By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	%			
	The government should take measures to restrict false information online, even if this limits press freedom.	Press freedom must be protected, even if false information is published.	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
All	65,5%	31,4%	3,0%	0,1%
Male	64,5%	33,5%	1,7%	0,3%
Female	66,6%	29,1%	4,3%	0,0%
17-24	61,3%	38,0%	0,7%	0,0%
25-34	68,6%	30,7%	0,3%	0,3%
35-44	73,0%	26,4%	0,3%	0,3%
45-54	73,0%	26,8%	0,2%	0,0%
55-64	65,7%	31,1%	3,2%	0,0%
65+	43,7%	41,8%	14,2%	0,3%
Low education	60,9%	31,5%	7,4%	0,2%
Medium education	67,5%	31,0%	1,5%	0,0%
High education	67,7%	31,6%	0,5%	0,3%
1 - Far-Left	59,4%	40,6%	0,0%	0,0%
2	66,3%	19,3%	14,5%	0,0%
3	60,9%	31,3%	7,5%	0,3%
4 - Center	70,3%	28,1%	1,6%	0,0%
5	61,7%	36,5%	1,7%	0,0%
6	59,9%	39,5%	0,0%	0,7%
7 - Far-Right	60,3%	38,4%	1,4%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Demographic patterns show that this preference is widely shared across society, though with some variation in intensity. Gender differences are modest: women (66,6%) are slightly more supportive of restrictive measures than men (64,5%), who are marginally more inclined to prioritise press freedom.

Age differences are more pronounced. Middle-aged groups (35–54) show the highest support for government intervention (73,0%), suggesting heightened concern about the societal risks of disinformation. In contrast, younger respondents (17–24) are somewhat more supportive of press freedom (38,0%), while the oldest group (65+) stands out for its ambivalence, with lower support for intervention (43,7%), higher support for press freedom (41,8%), and a notably large share of uncertainty (14,2%).

Education also plays a role, though differences are moderate. Support for government intervention increases slightly with education, from 60,9% among lower-educated respondents to around 67,0% among medium and highly educated groups, suggesting that higher educational attainment may be associated with greater concern about the harms of disinformation.

Political orientation introduces more nuanced variation but does not fundamentally alter the overall pattern. Support for government intervention remains the majority position across the spectrum, though it peaks among centrist respondents (70,3%). The far-left shows comparatively higher support for press freedom (40,6%), while the far-right also leans somewhat more toward press freedom (38,4%) than the center. This suggests that scepticism toward government intervention may emerge at both ideological extremes, albeit for potentially different reasons.

Overall, the findings point to a broad societal willingness to accept regulatory trade-offs in response to disinformation, though this is tempered by pockets of resistance—particularly among younger individuals, older respondents, and those at the ideological extremes, who remain more cautious about limiting press freedom. It should be noted that due to the historically high placing of Portugal press freedom-wise – 10th out of 180 countries (Reporters Without Borders, 2026), this trade-off is being gauged hypothetically. Since the establishment of the democratic regime in 1974 and of the enablement of the Portuguese Constitution in 1976 press freedom has remained a core value of the Portuguese democratic system, with a generalized perception of media as being impartial and independent from political and economic influence (Cardoso et al., 2023).

8.3. The actors behind disinformation

Considering the threats posed by different actors when it comes to disinformation, the results show that citizens attribute responsibility for disinformation primarily to digital-native actors, with influencers or online personalities emerging as the most widely perceived threat (53,8%) (table in next page). This places individual content creators at the centre of public concern, ahead of institutional or traditional actors.

A second tier of perceived threats includes lobbies or pressure groups (43,9%), politicians or political parties in one's own country (41,7%), and social media platform owners (41,7%), followed closely by foreign political actors (38,7%). This indicates that respondents perceive disinformation as both a domestic and international political phenomenon, while also recognising the enabling role of platforms.

More traditional actors are viewed as less central but still relevant. The media and journalists (36,4%), activists (36,1%), and ordinary people (32,0%) are identified by roughly one-third of respondents, suggesting a recognition that disinformation is not only top-down but also diffuse and socially embedded. By contrast, companies (19,3%) and public figures such as celebrities (28,6%) are less frequently seen as major threats.

Q18. [Disinformation actors] With regard to the false and misleading information circulating today in general, which of the following groups pose the greatest threat in terms of creating and/or spreading it? Please select all that apply., 2026 (%)

	%	
	Yes	No
Influencers / online personalities	53,8%	46,2%
Foreign governments, politicians or political parties	38,7%	61,3%
Politicians or political parties in my country	41,7%	58,3%
Lobbies or pressure groups	43,9%	56,1%
Companies	19,3%	80,7%
Social media platform owners	41,7%	58,3%
The media and journalists	36,4%	63,6%
Public figures (e.g. singers, sports stars...)	28,6%	71,4%
Activists or activist groups	36,1%	63,9%
Ordinary people	32,0%	68,0%
Others	1,8%	98,2%
None of the above [SINGLE ANSWER]	2,3%	97,7%
Don't know	5,8%	94,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,6%	99,4%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Demographic differences reveal important patterns. Perception of influencers as a threat increases significantly with education, from 42,9% among lower-educated respondents to 65,1% among the highly educated, suggesting greater awareness of digital information dynamics. Age also matters: middle-aged groups (45–64) show the highest concern across most actor categories, particularly regarding influencers and pressure groups, while younger respondents (17–24) consistently report lower levels of concern, especially toward institutional actors.

Political orientation introduces strong asymmetries. The far-left is considerably less likely to identify influencers (28,1%) or domestic political actors (28,1%) as threats, but more likely to point to foreign actors (43,8%). In contrast, respondents in the centre and moderate right (levels 4–6) show the highest levels of concern toward influencers, lobbies, and domestic political actors, suggesting a more systemic view of disinformation. Interestingly, the far-right shows comparatively lower concern toward social media platforms (30,6%) and lobbies (31,9%), but still identifies influencers (45,2%) as a major source.

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Q18. [Disinformation actors] With regard to the false and misleading information circulating today in general, which of the following groups pose the greatest threat in terms of creating and/or spreading it? Please select all that apply., By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	Influencers / online personalities	Foreign governments, politicians or political parties	Politicians or political parties in my country	Lobbies or pressure groups	Companies	Social media platform owners	The media and journalists	Public figures (e.g. singers, sports stars...)	Activists or activist groups	Ordinary people
All	53,8%	38,7%	41,7%	43,9%	19,3%	41,7%	36,4%	28,6%	36,1%	32,0%
Male	55,4%	41,8%	42,6%	48,3%	21,7%	41,7%	35,4%	30,0%	38,7%	29,7%
Female	52,6%	35,7%	41,0%	39,9%	17,2%	42,2%	37,7%	27,3%	33,8%	34,3%
17-24	43,7%	27,2%	35,8%	20,0%	20,7%	30,0%	36,4%	33,3%	23,8%	25,8%
25-34	46,3%	32,9%	44,4%	24,1%	23,8%	31,9%	36,6%	28,9%	24,5%	32,5%
35-44	55,0%	34,7%	40,8%	37,4%	20,6%	36,3%	35,8%	28,9%	32,6%	29,6%
45-54	63,8%	42,5%	46,4%	53,0%	21,5%	45,7%	38,0%	30,2%	43,2%	31,1%
55-64	56,9%	43,4%	40,8%	61,6%	18,7%	52,6%	35,8%	28,4%	43,1%	37,8%
65+	44,1%	41,3%	35,8%	43,7%	9,8%	42,4%	34,8%	23,5%	36,1%	30,7%
Low educ.	42,9%	36,7%	35,7%	31,8%	17,4%	39,7%	32,5%	23,4%	27,8%	28,3%
Medium educ.	53,2%	37,7%	39,2%	42,6%	20,6%	40,1%	40,1%	29,0%	38,8%	33,7%
High educ.	65,1%	41,6%	50,3%	56,9%	19,8%	45,7%	36,3%	33,3%	41,1%	33,6%
1 - Far-Left	28,1%	43,8%	28,1%	21,9%	12,5%	31,3%	15,6%	25,0%	21,9%	18,8%
2	43,4%	33,7%	47,0%	53,0%	20,5%	43,4%	22,9%	19,3%	26,5%	31,3%
3	54,7%	39,1%	42,7%	45,3%	14,8%	46,1%	32,6%	31,8%	33,2%	34,2%
4 - Center	54,3%	38,3%	41,0%	44,5%	20,8%	44,2%	35,4%	25,2%	33,8%	35,4%
5	58,5%	40,0%	43,6%	48,5%	19,6%	38,6%	40,3%	32,9%	44,1%	29,0%
6	57,8%	43,5%	41,5%	36,5%	21,1%	33,3%	51,0%	35,4%	46,3%	21,1%
7 - Far-Right	45,2%	34,2%	39,7%	31,9%	22,2%	30,6%	38,9%	30,1%	37,5%	28,8%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Overall, the findings point to a hybrid perception of disinformation responsibility, combining strong concern about individualised digital actors (influencers) with broader suspicion toward political, institutional, and platform-based sources. This reinforces the idea that citizens understand disinformation as a multi-actor ecosystem, though with clear emphasis on the role of online content creators.

These findings reflect those highlighted in literature of disinformation as a disorder sustained by the action of multiple actors (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017) though with a strong platform / network / technology undertone (van Dijck et al., 2018) in which these actor do not act isolatedly, even if their coordination is most of the time non-intentional and involuntary (Tucker et al., 2018).

9. Trust

9.1. The benefits and drawbacks of science and technology

Q19. If you had to take stock of science and technology, taking into account all the positive and negative aspects, which of the following options would best reflect your opinion?, 2026 (%)

	%
The benefits outweigh the drawbacks	46,5%
The benefits and drawbacks are balanced	36,5%
The drawbacks outweigh the benefits	15,9%
Don't know	0,9%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Considering the evaluation of the benefits and drawbacks of science and technology, the results indicate a predominantly positive but nuanced view of science and technology, with nearly half of respondents (46,5%) believing that the benefits outweigh the drawbacks, while a substantial proportion (36,5%) adopt a more balanced position. Only a minority (15,9%) consider that the drawbacks outweigh the benefits. This suggests that, although optimism prevails, there is also a significant degree of ambivalence and critical reflection.

Demographic patterns reveal meaningful differences (table in the next page). Men (51,7%) are more likely than women (42,1%) to express a clearly positive view, while women are more inclined to see benefits and drawbacks as balanced (39,5%) and slightly more likely to emphasise drawbacks (17,0%).

Age differences are relatively moderate, but younger groups (17–34) are more likely to adopt a balanced view, whereas older groups tend to lean slightly more toward the benefits outweighing drawbacks. However, scepticism (drawbacks outweigh benefits) remains fairly stable across age groups, around 16,0%.

Education emerges as a key dividing factor. Highly educated respondents are markedly more optimistic (61,3%), and significantly less likely to emphasise drawbacks (8,0%), compared to those with lower education, among whom only 34,4% see benefits outweighing drawbacks and 24,3% believe the opposite. This points to a strong association between education and confidence in scientific and technological progress.

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Q19. If you had to take stock of science and technology, taking into account all the positive and negative aspects, which of the following options would best reflect your opinion?, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (%)

	The benefits outweigh the drawbacks	The benefits and drawbacks are balanced	The drawbacks outweigh the benefits	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
All	46,5%	36,5%	15,9%	0,9%	0,2%
Male	51,7%	32,8%	14,8%	0,7%	0,1%
Female	42,1%	39,5%	17,0%	1,2%	0,2%
17-24	44,0%	40,0%	16,0%	0,0%	0,0%
25-34	41,0%	42,2%	16,5%	0,0%	0,3%
35-44	47,7%	38,4%	13,9%	0,0%	0,0%
45-54	48,3%	35,5%	16,2%	0,0%	0,0%
55-64	47,6%	33,4%	16,5%	2,0%	0,5%
65+	47,3%	33,0%	16,2%	3,5%	0,0%
Low education	34,4%	39,8%	24,3%	1,4%	0,0%
Medium education	43,7%	38,8%	15,9%	1,4%	0,3%
High education	61,3%	30,5%	8,0%	0,0%	0,2%
1 - Far-Left	29,0%	32,3%	38,7%	0,0%	0,0%
2	39,0%	35,4%	25,6%	0,0%	0,0%
3	51,8%	31,8%	13,2%	3,2%	0,0%
4 - Center	44,5%	39,1%	15,6%	0,6%	0,2%
5	53,2%	34,2%	12,1%	0,5%	0,0%
6	37,8%	45,9%	15,5%	0,0%	0,7%
7 - Far-Right	45,2%	26,0%	28,8%	0,0%	0,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Political orientation introduces the most pronounced contrasts. The far-left stands out as the most sceptical group, with only 29.0% believing benefits outweigh drawbacks and a plurality (38.7%) stating the opposite. Moving toward the centre and moderate right (levels 3–5), optimism increases substantially, peaking at 53.2% among those at level 5. The far-right shows a more ambivalent pattern, with 45.2% positive but also a relatively high share (28.8%) emphasising drawbacks, alongside a strong preference for balanced views among those just below the far-right (level 6).

Overall, the findings point to a broad but uneven optimism toward science and technology, structured strongly by education and political orientation. While most citizens recognise their benefits, a sizeable share—particularly among less educated and ideologically extreme groups—expresses critical or sceptical attitudes, reflecting ongoing tensions in how technological change is perceived. The consideration of the negative and positive impacts of science, technology and of development in general has been widely covered by the risk society theoretical propositions (Beck, 1992) but resonates strongly with the discussion at hand, due to the anxiety inducing aspects of AI (Qian et al. 2024).

It should be noted that the dynamics behind the perception of science are, in these terms of discussion, multifactorial in nature and, most importantly, that even neutral positioning towards science may have different causes, in the sense that not all skepticism is equal and largely dependent on context (Rutjens et al., 2018).

9.2. Trust in others

Q20. Would you say that, as a rule, one can never be too careful when dealing with others, or that you can trust most people? Please rate yourself on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 means “one can never be too careful” and 7 means “you can trust most people”. 2026 (% and Means)

	%
1 - You can never be too careful	13,7%
2	9,2%
3	18,3%
4	35,1%
5	17,3%
6	2,9%
7 - You can trust most people	3,4%
Don't know	0,0%
I'd rather not answer	0,0%
	Mean
Mean	3,55

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Analysing the trust that respondents place on others, the results point to a moderate but cautious level of interpersonal trust, with an overall mean of 3,55 on a 1–7 scale, slightly below the midpoint. This suggests that respondents lean slightly toward the idea that “one can never be too careful”, rather than fully trusting others.

The distribution reinforces this interpretation. The largest share of respondents (35,1%) choose the midpoint (4), indicating ambivalence, while a combined 41,2% fall on the more cautious side (1–3) compared to 23,6% on the more trusting side (5–7). Strong trust is relatively rare, with only 3,4% selecting the highest category. Demographic patterns reveal systematic variation (table in the next page). Men (3,70) report higher levels of trust than women (3,41), indicating a modest gender gap in perceived social trust. Age differences are

also pronounced: younger respondents (17–24=3,85, 25–34=3,75) are the most trusting, while trust declines steadily with age, reaching its lowest level among those aged 65+ (3,28).

Q20. Would you say that, as a rule, one can never be too careful when dealing with others, or that you can trust most people? Please rate yourself on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 means “one can never be too careful” and 7 means “you can trust most people”. By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Means
All	3,55
Male	3,70
Female	3,41
17-24	3,85
25-34	3,75
35-44	3,54
45-54	3,53
55-64	3,54
65+	3,28
Low education	3,43
Medium education	3,51
High education	3,72
1 - Far-Left	2,97
2	3,01
3	3,53
4 - Center	3,51
5	3,73
6	3,55
7 - Far-Right	4,02

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scalem ranges between 1-You can never be too careful and 7-You can trust most people.

Education is positively associated with trust. Highly educated respondents (3,72) exhibit higher trust levels than those with medium (3,51) or low education (3,43), suggesting that education may foster greater confidence in others or in social institutions more broadly. Political orientation shows one of the clearest gradients. The far-left displays the lowest levels of trust (2,97), followed by those at level 2 (3,01), indicating a strong orientation toward caution. Trust increases progressively toward the centre and moderate right, peaking at 4,02 among the far-right, the only group clearly above the midpoint. This suggests that ideological positioning is strongly linked to generalized trust, with right-leaning individuals expressing more confidence in others than left-leaning respondents.

In general, the results portray a society characterised by cautious trust, where ambivalence dominates and strong trust is limited. Differences by age, education, and especially political orientation indicate that interpersonal trust is unevenly distributed, potentially shaping how individuals engage with information, institutions, and each other. The analytical framework for interpersonal trust used in this context, understood as the belief that other people can be relied upon, constitutes a central component of social capital and democratic functioning, but can be affected by information environments characterised by misinformation and polarisation (Putnam, 2000, Uslaner, 2002, Lewandowsky et al., 2023).

9.3. Trust in institutions

Q21. To what extent do you trust the following institutions or groups to tackle issues related to science and technology, health or the environment: a lot, quite a bit, a little or nothing?, 2026 (% and Means)

	%							
	P2 1.1 The Portuguese Government	P2 1.2 Regional Governments (depending on residence)	P2 1.3 Politicians	P2 1.4 The United Nations / World Health Organization (WHO)	P2 1.5 European Union	P2 1.6 Journals	P2 1.7 Scientists	P2 1.8 IP MA (Portuguese Institute of Science and Technology)
1 – Nothing	16,1%	14,0%	30,5%	11,3%	11,2%	13,0%	4,0%	4,9%
2 – A little	45,2%	47,4%	51,9%	35,0%	38,2%	46,4%	21,7%	22,9%
3 – Quite a bit	30,5%	32,0%	12,2%	41,5%	41,8%	35,1%	54,1%	51,9%
4 – A lot	5,7%	4,4%	2,1%	10,1%	6,5%	4,1%	18,8%	19,2%
Don't know	0,6%	0,5%	1,6%	2,1%	1,8%	1,3%	1,3%	0,7%
I'd rather not answer	1,9%	1,7%	1,7%	0,1%	0,5%	0,2%	0,1%	0,3%
	Means							
Mean	2,26	2,27	1,85	2,52	2,45	2,31	2,89	2,86

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Considering the landscape of institutional trust, the results reveal a stratified landscape of institutional trust, with clear differences between scientific actors, international organisations, and political institutions. Overall, trust levels remain moderate, but no institution reaches a strongly positive evaluation, indicating a generally cautious public attitude.

At the aggregate level, scientists (mean=2,89) and IPMA – the Portuguese Institute of the Sea and the Atmosphere (2,86) emerge as the most trusted actors. A majority of respondents express relatively high confidence in these groups, with over half indicating “quite a bit” of trust (54,1% for scientists, 51,9% for IPMA) and comparatively high shares selecting “a lot” (18,8% and 19,2%, respectively). This positions scientific and technical expertise as the most credible source of authority in addressing issues related to science, health, and the environment.

A second tier includes international and supranational institutions, namely the United Nations / World Health Organisation (2,52) and the European Union (2,45). These actors benefit from relatively balanced trust profiles, with around 40,0% of respondents expressing “quite a bit” of trust, though fewer select the highest category. Trust in these institutions is thus present but not overwhelmingly strong, reflecting a degree of legitimacy combined with some scepticism.

By contrast, national political actors are the least trusted. Politicians receive the lowest mean score (1,85), with 30,5% expressing no trust at all and a majority (51,9%) indicating only “a little” trust. Similarly, the Portuguese government (2,26) and regional / autonomous governments (2,27) are viewed more sceptically than scientific or international actors, with pluralities selecting “a little” trust. Journalists (2,31) occupy an intermediate position but lean closer to political institutions than to scientific actors. Nearly half of respondents (46,4%) report trusting journalists only “a little”, suggesting persistent concerns about media credibility, although outright distrust remains lower than for politicians.

*Q21. To what extent do you trust the following institutions or groups to tackle issues related to science and technology, health or the environment: a lot, quite a bit, a little or nothing?,
By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)*

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	P2 1.1 The Portuguese Government	P2 1.2 Regional / Autonomous Governments (depending on region of residence)	P2 1.3 Politicians	P2 1.4 The United Nations / World Health Organization (WHO)	P2 1.5 European Union	P2 1.6 Journalists	P2 1.7 Scientists	P2 1.8 IP MA (Portuguese Institute of the Sea and the Atmosphere)
All	2,26	2,27	1,85	2,52	2,45	2,31	2,89	2,86
Male	2,29	2,29	1,88	2,48	2,43	2,30	2,92	2,84
Female	2,24	2,26	1,83	2,55	2,46	2,31	2,87	2,89
17-24	2,26	2,33	2,07	2,68	2,56	2,35	2,74	2,72
25-34	2,20	2,24	1,92	2,48	2,45	2,17	2,71	2,70
35-44	2,18	2,23	1,87	2,55	2,52	2,28	2,86	2,78
45-54	2,20	2,17	1,78	2,52	2,40	2,27	2,90	2,87
55-64	2,33	2,31	1,86	2,54	2,41	2,42	2,96	2,95
65+	2,47	2,49	1,79	2,39	2,44	2,38	3,08	3,08
Low education	2,23	2,26	1,81	2,35	2,32	2,30	2,76	2,81
Medium education	2,20	2,20	1,82	2,48	2,39	2,26	2,83	2,83
High education	2,36	2,37	1,93	2,71	2,63	2,37	3,08	2,95
1 – Far-Left	2,28	2,21	1,88	2,54	2,50	2,39	2,63	2,84
2	2,12	2,25	1,76	2,39	2,25	2,21	2,88	2,90
3	2,33	2,33	1,86	2,66	2,52	2,41	2,99	2,94
4 – Center	2,24	2,26	1,83	2,51	2,45	2,29	2,84	2,85
5	2,35	2,29	1,91	2,53	2,49	2,32	3,02	2,92
6	2,09	2,22	1,73	2,30	2,30	2,12	2,90	2,78
7 – Far-Right	2,18	2,24	1,99	2,24	2,18	2,31	2,58	2,77

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1 to 4 where 1-Nothing and 4-A lot.

Demographic patterns reinforce these hierarchies. Trust in scientists and IPMA increases with age and education, peaking among older and highly educated respondents (means above 3,0). Conversely, trust in political institutions remains consistently low across all groups, with only marginal variation.

Political orientation introduces further nuance. While trust in scientists remains relatively high across the spectrum, far-right respondents tend to express slightly lower trust in international institutions (UN / WHO=2,24, EU=2,18) compared to centre or left-leaning individuals. Meanwhile, trust in national institutions varies less dramatically but remains subdued overall.

In sum, the findings indicate a clear hierarchy of trust: scientific and technical institutions are more trusted than international organisations which overcome, in order, media and national political actors. This pattern underscores the central role of expertise-based authority, while highlighting deep-seated scepticism toward political institutions, which may have implications for policy communication and public compliance in areas such as health and environmental governance. The results fall in line with historical data highlighted in the Edelman Trust Barometer, where scientists and teachers (those who handle knowledge) gather considerably higher trust evaluations from citizens than politicians or the media (Edelman Trust Institute, 2026).

10. Scientific populism

10.1. Science and society

Q22. The following statements refer to the relationship between science and society. To what extent do you agree or disagree with them?, 2026 (% and Means)

	%					
	Q22.1 Scientists are only interested in their own benefit.	Q22.2 Scientists are in cahoots with politicians and businesses.	Q22.3 Ordinary people should have a say in the work of scientists.	Q22.4 Ordinary people should be involved in decisions about the topics scientists investigate.	Q22.5 Ordinary people should rely more on their own life experience than on scientists' recommendations.	Q22.6 Our society should rely more on common sense than on scientific studies.
1 – Strongly disagree	17,8%	7,4%	16,1%	13,7%	14,0%	19,1%
2	17,2%	11,2%	14,5%	13,8%	13,4%	15,6%
3	21,7%	16,3%	14,6%	15,3%	15,8%	15,8%
4	23,9%	29,9%	28,0%	26,0%	28,7%	24,9%
5	11,5%	17,4%	15,1%	16,7%	16,7%	12,9%
6	3,7%	8,9%	6,4%	8,2%	6,4%	6,2%
7 – Strongly agree	3,7%	7,0%	4,8%	5,7%	4,7%	5,1%
Don't know	0,5%	1,8%	0,5%	0,6%	0,3%	0,4%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
	Means					
Mean	3,20	3,95	3,00	3,66	3,59	3,36

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Considering the relationship between science and society, respondents were asked about their level of agreement with a series of statements related to the way in which science interacts with other social spheres, as well as about the role of citizens in defining scientific agendas. The data points to a complex and somewhat ambivalent relationship between science, expertise, and society, combining moderate trust in scientific authority with significant scepticism about scientists' independence and strong support for public involvement in decision-making in the scientific sphere.

At the aggregate level, the most strongly supported statement is Q22.2 ("Scientists are in cahoots with politicians and businesses") (mean=3,95). This relatively high score, close to the midpoint but leaning toward agreement, indicates a widespread suspicion regarding the

independence of scientific actors, suggesting that many respondents perceive science as entangled with political and economic interests.

By contrast, Q22.3 (“Ordinary people should have a say in the work of scientists”) (3,00) records the lowest mean, although still around the midpoint. This suggests that while public participation is supported, it is not overwhelmingly endorsed as a primary principle guiding scientific work. More broadly, respondents express moderate agreement with participatory and experiential approaches to knowledge. Both Q22.4 (involvement of ordinary people in decisions) (3,66) and Q22.5 (valuing lived experience alongside scientific recommendations) (3,59) receive relatively high scores, alluding to a hybrid epistemological model in which scientific expertise is respected but not seen as sufficient on its own.

At the same time, there is some endorsement of scientific authority, as reflected in Q22.6 (“society should rely more on scientific studies than on common sense”) (3,36). However, the moderate level of agreement suggests that science is not viewed as the sole or dominant source of legitimate knowledge, but rather as one component among others, which is not always reflected in the way scientists place and present themselves in the public sphere.

The statement Q22.1 (“Scientists are only interested in their own benefit”) (3,20) also receives a mid-range score, reinforcing the idea of latent scepticism toward scientists’ motivations, though not as strongly as the perception of institutional entanglement captured in Q22.2.

Demographic patterns deepen this interpretation (table in next page). Younger respondents (17–24) show higher agreement with participatory and sceptical statements (e.g. 4,39 on Q22.2), indicating a more critical and engaged stance toward science. Conversely, older groups (65+) display lower agreement with these sceptical views (3,30 on Q22.2) and slightly more reliance on scientific authority, suggesting a more deferential orientation toward expertise.

Education also plays a key role. Lower-educated respondents consistently show higher agreement across most statements, including scepticism toward scientists and support for public involvement, whereas higher-educated individuals are more restrained, particularly regarding claims about scientists’ self-interest or collusion with political and / or economic power.

The most striking divide emerges along political lines. Far-right respondents exhibit systematically higher agreement across all statements, including both sceptical claims (e.g. 5,22 on Q22.2) and participatory positions (e.g. 4,84 on Q22.4). This indicates a strongly politicised critique of scientific authority, possibly combined with support for alternative forms of knowledge. In contrast, far-left respondents display the lowest levels of agreement, suggesting comparatively higher trust in scientific institutions and less endorsement of anti-elitist framings.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Q22. The following statements refer to the relationship between science and society. To what extent do you agree or disagree with them?, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Q22.1 Scientists are only interested in their own benefit.	Q22.2 Scientists are in cahoots with politicians and businesses.	Q22.3 Ordinary people should have a say in the work of scientists.	Q22.4 Ordinary people should be involved in decisions about the topics scientists investigate.	Q22.5 Ordinary people should rely more on their own life experience than on scientists' recommendations.	Q22.6 Our society should rely more on common sense than on scientific studies.
All	3,20	3,95	3,00	3,66	3,59	3,36
Male	3,24	4,00	3,58	3,74	3,73	3,48
Female	3,17	3,91	3,43	3,58	3,46	3,23
17-24	3,25	4,39	3,77	4,01	3,74	3,60
25-34	3,29	4,12	3,83	3,76	3,48	3,42
35-44	3,31	4,01	3,56	3,68	3,44	3,23
45-54	3,35	4,07	3,50	3,69	3,65	3,29
55-64	3,11	3,92	3,40	3,70	3,68	3,39
65+	2,82	3,30	3,09	3,28	3,55	3,40
Low education	3,40	3,97	3,61	3,80	3,89	3,73
Medium education	3,27	4,10	3,67	3,80	3,73	3,52
High education	2,95	3,79	3,22	3,38	3,15	2,85
1 – Far-Left	2,40	2,78	2,87	3,36	3,32	3,60
2	2,78	3,38	3,19	3,23	3,04	2,80
3	2,88	3,70	3,28	3,39	3,33	3,18
4 – Center	3,20	3,99	3,51	3,70	3,61	3,34
5	3,25	3,89	3,50	3,71	3,61	3,32
6	3,59	4,22	3,60	3,60	3,75	3,59
7 – Far-Right	4,53	5,22	4,55	4,84	4,73	4,56

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1-Strongly disagree and 7-Strongly agree.

Overall, the findings reveal a hybrid and contested epistemic landscape: science remains an important and relatively trusted source of knowledge, but it is simultaneously subject to suspicion, demands for democratisation, and competition from experiential forms of understanding. The discussion about the need for a deeper integration between the

scientific sphere and wider society is old (Royal Society, 1985, Irwin, 1995). The prevalence of a top-down approach solidifies into a condescending stance between scientists and citizens, in which the former inform the latter but without truly engaging in a meaningful way (Irwin & Wynne, 1996). As such, research calls for greater public engagement, co-production of knowledge, and more socially embedded forms of scientific practice (Bucchi & Trench, 2021, Jasanoff, 2005, Nowotny et al., 2001).

10.2. Sharing scientific opinions

Q23. *[Sharing scientific views] Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements; 2026 (% and Means)*

	%		
	P23.1 I would share my views on scientific issues, regardless of what others think.	P23.2 I would share my views on scientific issues, even if this might lead to me becoming more isolated from others.	P23.3 I would share my views on scientific issues, even if I think others are against those views.
1- Strongly disagree	9,6%	9,5%	8,3%
2	9,8%	8,8%	8,3%
3	13,5%	12,7%	12,1%
4	24,8%	24,7%	25,0%
5	18,8%	19,7%	20,5%
6	9,5%	11,3%	11,2%
7 – Strongly agree	12,1%	11,3%	12,9%
Don't know	1,8%	1,8%	1,8%
I'd rather not answer	0,1%	0,1%	0,1%
	Means		
Mean	4,13	4,18	4,29

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Analysing the perspectives on the sharing of scientific opinions the results indicate a relatively strong willingness among respondents to express their views on scientific issues, even in potentially adverse social contexts or reactions. Across all three statements, mean scores are above the midpoint, suggesting that public expression on science-related topics is generally normalised rather than inhibited.

At the aggregate level, the highest agreement is observed for Q23.3 (“I would share my views even if others are against those views”) (mean=4,29). This suggests a high degree of perceived resilience to social disagreement, indicating that respondents are relatively comfortable expressing dissenting opinions on scientific matters.

Similarly, Q23.2 (willingness to share views even at the risk of social isolation) (4,18) also scores relatively high, reinforcing the idea that social costs do not strongly deter expression. Meanwhile, Q23.1, relating to sharing views regardless of what others think (4,13), although slightly lower, still reflects a broadly assertive communicative stance.

The distribution of responses further supports this interpretation: the largest shares cluster around the midpoint (category 4), but combined agreement categories (5–7) consistently outweigh disagreement (1–3) across all items. This points to a moderate but clear inclination toward open expression, rather than hesitancy.

Q23. [Sharing scientific views] Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements:, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	P23.1 I would share my views on scientific issues, regardless of what others think.	P23.2 I would share my views on scientific issues, even if this might lead to me becoming more isolated from others.	P23.3 I would share my views on scientific issues, even if I think others are against those views.
All	4,13	4,18	4,29
Male	4,19	4,31	4,40
Femaie	4,07	4,04	4,17
17-24	3,68	4,27	4,37
25-34	3,85	4,15	4,21
35-44	4,16	4,23	4,40
45-54	4,16	4,16	4,22
55-64	4,42	4,25	4,36
65+	4,17	4,03	4,21
Low education	4,04	4,04	4,12
Medium education	4,09	4,17	4,29
High education	4,25	4,31	4,44
1 – Far-Left	3,69	3,35	3,52
2	4,23	4,37	4,41
3	4,06	4,11	4,18
4 – Center	4,09	4,06	4,15
5	4,12	4,24	4,39
6	4,21	4,41	4,51
7 – Far-Right	4,79	4,94	5,29

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1-Strongly disagree and 7-Strongly agree.

Demographic patterns show some variation but largely reinforce the overall trend. Men report slightly higher willingness to share views than women, particularly in more conflictual scenarios (e.g. 4,40 against 4,17 in Q23.3). Age differences are more nuanced: younger respondents (17–24) are less likely to share views “regardless of others” (3,68) but show relatively high willingness when framed in terms of disagreement or isolation, suggesting a context-dependent communicative behaviour.

Education is positively associated with willingness to express opinions. Higher-educated respondents consistently score highest across all items (e.g. 4,44 in Q23.3), indicating that confidence or engagement with scientific issues may facilitate public expression.

The most pronounced differences emerge along political lines. Far-right respondents display markedly higher agreement across all statements, particularly in conflictual scenarios (5,29 in Q23.3, 4.94 in Q23.2). This suggests a strong propensity toward assertive and potentially confrontational expression of views on scientific issues. In contrast, far-left respondents show the lowest levels of agreement (e.g., 3.52 in P23.3), indicating a more restrained or context-sensitive approach to public expression.

Overall, the findings point to a public sphere in which individuals are generally willing to voice opinions on science, even in the face of disagreement or social pressure. However, this openness is unevenly distributed, with political orientation emerging as the strongest differentiating factor, potentially shaping not only what people believe about science, but also how they engage in its public discussion. The aspects relating to the willingness to share scientific opinions or to gauge scientific knowledge as an argument are of particularly salient importance in the current social and political environment.

Science is often mobilised as a rhetorical resource, where actors selectively invoke or contest expertise to support pre-existing positions or to deligitimise the opinion of others, a process linked to motivated reasoning and the politicisation of science (Bolsen & Druckman, 2018, Gieryn, 1983). In polarised political environments, the groupal aspect behind the weaponisation of science is of greater relevance as, in the face of uncertainty, people shape their perspectives on the moral evaluations they share with others (Kahan, 2012) while at the same time having the predisposition to reject information that opposes the epistemological configurations of the groups they belong to (Kahan, 2011, Kahan, 2017).

Kahan (2012) raises an interesting argument regarding the potentially polarising power of knowledge: unlike what is argued in the “deficit model” (Brown, 2009) (people disagree due to lack of knowledge), the author demonstrates that individuals with higher literacy profiles in numeracy / science are more prone to polarisation as they gauge their cognitive skills and knowledge to selectively filter data that confirms their political views (Kahan, 2012). Kahan’s findings are of particular centrality to this discussion as the core references were based on research on topics such as environment, climate and environmental catastrophes.

10.3. Society and its subgroups

Observing the attitudes towards subgroups in society, data points to a strong normative commitment to equality between groups, combined with residual ambivalence and clear ideological polarisation, particularly regarding hierarchical and anti-egalitarian views.

At the aggregate level, the strongest agreement is observed for Q24.1 (“When setting priorities, we should consider all groups”) (mean=5,08) and Q24.3 (“Equality between groups should be our ideal”) (5,06). Both statements receive high levels of endorsement, with large shares selecting agreement categories (5–7), including 28,3% and 27,2% “strongly agree”, respectively. This indicates that egalitarian principles are widely supported and form a central normative baseline in public opinion.

In contrast, Q24.4 (“Superior groups should dominate inferior groups”) (2,40) is overwhelmingly rejected. Nearly half of respondents (47,1%) “strongly disagree”, and agreement levels are extremely low (only 2,7% “strongly agree”), pointing to a clear rejection of explicitly hierarchical or supremacist views.

However, attitudes become more nuanced when considering Q24.2 (“We should not push for equality between groups”) (3,74). While the mean remains below the midpoint, indicating overall disagreement, the relatively high score compared to Q24.4 suggests a degree of ambivalence or resistance toward active equality-promoting policies, even among individuals who support equality as a principle. This reflects a distinction between endorsing equality normatively and supporting interventions to achieve it.

Q24. Societies are divided into groups: men and women, ethnic and religious groups, nationalities, political factions, etc. In general, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following ideas about groups?. 2026 (% and Means)

	%			
	Q24.1 When setting priorities, we should consider all groups.	Q24.2 We should not push for equality between groups.	Q24.3 Equality between groups should be our ideal.	Q24.4 Superior groups should dominate inferior groups.
1- Strongly disagree	3,9%	16,4%	3,7%	47,1%
2	4,2%	11,4%	4,1%	14,3%
3	9,5%	12,7%	8,1%	10,6%
4	18,6%	25,6%	21,0%	15,4%
5	18,0%	14,5%	18,9%	6,8%
6	17,3%	8,8%	16,5%	2,8%
7 – Strongly agree	28,3%	9,1%	27,2%	2,7%
Don't know	0,0%	1,3%	0,1%	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%	0,2%	0,3%	0,1%
	Means			
Mean	5,08	3,74	5,06	2,40

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Demographic patterns reinforce these dynamics. Older respondents (65+) express the strongest support for egalitarian principles (e.g. 5,88 in Q24.1, 5,76 in Q24.3) and the lowest acceptance of hierarchical views (1,89 in Q24.4). Younger respondents (17–24), while still broadly egalitarian, show slightly weaker support for equality and higher openness to hierarchical framing (3,28 in Q24.4), suggesting a more fluid or less consolidated normative stance.

Education also plays a role. Higher-educated individuals display stronger endorsement of equality (5,17 in Q24.3) and lower agreement with hierarchical views (2,17 in Q24.4), while lower-educated respondents show slightly more ambivalence, particularly regarding equality-promoting measures (3,78 in Q24.2).

Q24. Societies are divided into groups: men and women, ethnic and religious groups, nationalities, political factions, etc. In general, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following ideas about groups?, By Gender, Age, Education and Political Orientation, 2026 (Means)

	Q24.1 When setting priorities, we should consider all groups.	Q24.2 We should not push for equality between groups.	Q24.3 Equality between groups should be our ideal.	Q24.4 Superior groups should dominate inferior groups.
All	5,08	3,74	5,06	2,40
Male	4,96	3,97	5,01	2,62
Female	5,21	3,52	5,13	2,16
17-24	4,16	3,86	4,70	3,28
25-34	4,53	3,79	4,90	2,83
35-44	4,86	3,77	4,76	2,55
45-54	5,13	3,92	4,90	2,32
55-64	5,34	3,70	5,25	2,09
65+	5,88	3,35	5,76	1,89
Low education	4,96	3,78	5,04	2,51
Medium education	4,96	3,95	4,99	2,50
High education	5,33	3,49	5,17	2,17
1 – Far-Left	4,62	3,22	4,63	2,37
2	5,58	2,82	5,83	1,71
3	5,32	3,32	5,46	2,01
4 – Center	5,10	3,65	5,02	2,31
5	5,02	4,07	4,96	2,57
6	4,77	4,23	4,60	2,85
7 – Far-Right	4,78	4,73	4,76	3,72

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031. Note: Scale ranges from 1 to 7 where 1-Strongly disagree and 7-Strongly agree.

The most pronounced differences emerge along political orientation. While support for equality (Q24.1 and Q24.3) is relatively high across the spectrum, far-right respondents diverge sharply on hierarchical and anti-egalitarian statements. They show the highest agreement with Q24.2 (4,73) and Q24.4 (3,72), indicating a greater openness to inequality and hierarchical ordering between groups. In contrast, far-left respondents exhibit the strongest rejection of these views (e.g. 2,37 in Q24.4) and lower agreement with anti-equality positions (3,22 in Q24.2). Interestingly, centrist and moderate groups tend to cluster around the overall average, suggesting that polarisation is primarily driven by the ideological extremes, particularly the far-right.

Overall, the findings point to a broad societal consensus around equality as a normative ideal and significant ideological divides on hierarchical social order. Portugal scores high in terms of the support for egalitarian values, support for resource distribution as well as in the openness to granting social rights and welfare access to immigrants (ESS ERIC, 2023).

11. Internet Usage

Q25. On average, how often have you used the Internet in the last 3 months? (Please include access from any location and using any device: computer, laptop, tablet, mobile phone, etc.), 2026 (%)

	%
1 – Several times a day	69,0%
2 – Every day or almost every day	17,9%
3 – At least once a week, but not every day	7,3%
4 – Less than once a week	5,1%
5 – I have not used the Internet in the last three months	0,0%
Don't know	0,4%
I'd rather not answer	0,2%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Analysing Internet usage data, results depict a highly connected and functionally integrated digital society, where intensive internet use coexists with moderate—rather than high—levels of trust. Starting with frequency of use, internet access is deeply embedded in everyday life. A striking 69,0% report using the internet several times a day, and an additional 17,9% use it daily or almost daily, meaning nearly 87,0% are daily users. Occasional use is marginal, and non-use is virtually nonexistent (0,0%), confirming the near-universal penetration of digital connectivity. These patterns fall in line with consistent data from the national Portuguese Digital News Report, which identifies a vast majority of the population as being “always on” (Cardoso et al., 2025).

Q26. In general, please indicate your level of trust in the Internet:, 2026 (%)

	%
1 – Little or none	24,3%
2 – Quite a lot	63,5%
3 – A lot	10,1%
Don't know	1,3%
I'd rather not answer	0,8%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Despite this pervasive use, trust in the internet remains moderate rather than strong. The majority (63,5%) report trusting the internet “quite a lot,” but only 10,1% express high trust, while a substantial 24,3% report little or no trust. This distribution suggests a pragmatic relationship with digital environments: people rely heavily on the internet in practice, yet maintain reservations about its reliability, safety, or credibility. As pointed out earlier, trust in sources and gateways for content ranges considerably according to the sources in question although it is clear that there is considerably less trust in the internet as a whole, compared

to legacy media and, in more fragmented terms, in search engines and social media, in particular (Cardoso et al., 2025).

Q27. Please indicate whether, in the last 3 months, you have used the Internet, via any device (including apps), to carry out any of the following activities for personal reasons; 2026 (%)

	Yes	No	Don't know	I'd rather not answer
P27.1 Participating in social media (creating a profile, sending messages or other posts on Facebook, TikTok, X, Instagram, etc.)	71,4%	28,4%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.2 Expressing opinions on civic or political issues on websites or social media (e.g. Facebook, X, Instagram, YouTube)	31,3%	68,5%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.3 Watching video content on sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Twitch, etc.)	75,5%	24,4%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.4 Watching films or videos on demand from commercial providers (Netflix, HBO Max, Prime Video, Disney+, Apple TV, Sky, Filmin, etc.)	56,9%	43,0%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.5 Searching for information on health topics (injuries, illnesses, nutrition, improving health, etc.)	73,3%	26,6%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.6 Selling goods or services online (e.g. OLX, Amazon, Vinted, FNAC, eBay, Facebook)	40,5%	59,3%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.7 Reading news on news websites, online newspapers or current affairs magazines	72,3%	27,5%	0,1%	0,1%
P27.8 Using online banking services (including mobile banking)	77,4%	22,2%	0,3%	0,1%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

The high level of internet usage translates into diverse and routine online activities, though with clear differences across domains. The most widespread uses are online banking (77,4%), watching online video content (75,5%), searching for health information (73,3%), reading news (72,3%), and participating in social media (71,4%). These figures suggest that the internet is not only a communication tool but also a key infrastructure for information, services, and everyday management.

However, more active or expressive uses are less common. Only 31,3% report expressing opinions on civic or political issues online, indicating that while consumption and functional use are widespread, participatory or deliberative engagement remains limited. Similarly, selling goods or services online (40.5%) is less frequent, pointing to uneven adoption of more transactional or entrepreneurial uses.

Taken together, these findings highlight a central paradox of contemporary digital societies: the internet is indispensable in everyday life, yet it is not fully trusted. This gap between usage and trust is particularly relevant in the context of disinformation, as it suggests that individuals may continue to engage extensively with online environments even while recognising their risks, reinforcing the importance of media literacy, platform governance, and trust-building mechanisms.

11. Demographics

[Gender] How would you describe yourself?

	Frequency	Percent
Male	983	48,8%
Female	1027	50,9%
Other	6	0,3%
Total	2017	100.0
System	14	0,7%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. N=2031.

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Age	Frequency	Percent
17	2	0,1%	46	57	2,8%
18	3	0,1%	47	47	2,3%
19	25	1,2%	48	65	3,2%
20	24	1,2%	49	48	2,4%
21	24	1,2%	50	47	2,3%
22	24	1,2%	51	55	2,7%
23	33	1,6%	52	59	2,9%
24	15	0,7%	53	54	2,7%
25	28	1,4%	54	37	1,8%
26	41	2,0%	55	49	2,4%
27	36	1,8%	56	39	1,9%
28	25	1,2%	57	44	2,2%
29	25	1,2%	58	50	2,5%
30	26	1,3%	59	44	2,2%
31	27	1,3%	60	51	2,5%
32	36	1,8%	61	37	1,8%
33	37	1,8%	62	25	1,2%
34	40	2,0%	63	34	1,7%
35	26	1,3%	64	28	1,4%
36	31	1,5%	65	26	1,3%
37	29	1,4%	66	31	1,5%
38	21	1,0%	67	41	2,0%
39	32	1,6%	68	38	1,9%
40	24	1,2%	69	24	1,2%
41	27	1,3%	70	25	1,2%
42	45	2,2%	71	37	1,8%
43	40	2,0%	72	32	1,6%
44	34	1,7%	73	11	0,5%
45	62	3,1%	74	50	2,5%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Age by Groups

	Frequency	Percent
17-24	151	7,4%
25-34	323	15,9%
35-44	311	15,3%
45-54	530	26,1%
55-64	401	19,8%
65+	315	15,5%
Total	2031	100%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. N=2031.

Education

	Frequency	Percent
Estudos primários incompletos ou menos	87	4,3%
Ensino básico – 1.º ciclo	141	6,9%
Ensino básico – 2.º/3.º ciclos	405	19,9%
Ensino secundário (incluindo profissional)	674	33,2%
CET / CteSP / Curso técnico superior profissional	61	3,0%
Licenciatura (1.º ciclo)	413	20,4%
Mestrado ou Doutoramento (2.º/3.º ciclos)	248	12,2%
Prefiro não responder	2	0,1%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Education by Groups

	Frequency	Percent
Low education	633	31,1%
Medium education	735	36,2%
High education	661	32,6%
Don't know	2	0,1%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Household income [Given that your net household income is around €1,700 a month, your household income is...]

	Frequency	Percent
Much higher (more than double)	121	6,0%
Higher	591	29,1%
Around that figure	567	27,9%
Lower	555	27,3%
Significantly lower (less than half)	167	8,2%
Don't know	5	0,3%
I'd rather not answer	25	1,2%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Household income by Groups [Given that your net household income is around €1,700 a month, your household income is...]

	Frequency	Percent
Above average	712	35,1%
Average – around that figure	567	27,9%
Below average	722	35,5%
Don't know	5	0,2%
I'd rather not answer	25	1,2%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Religious identification

	Frequency	Percent
Practising Catholic	329	16,2%
Non-practising Catholic	926	45,6%
Believer of another religion	147	7,2%
Indifferent or agnostic	329	16,2%
Atheist	224	11,0%
Total	1954	
Missings	77	
Total sample	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Do you consider yourself more of a humanities person or a science person?

	Frequency	Percent
More humanities	1022	50,3%
More sciences	922	45,4%
Both	28	1,4%
Neither	29	1,4%
Don't know	31	1,5%
Total	2031	100%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Political orientation – When talking about politics, espo common to use the terms 'left' and 'right'. On a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 means 'far-left' and 7 means 'far-right', where would you place yourself?

	Frequency	Percent
1 – Far-left	32	2%
2	83	4%
3	371	18%
4	852	42%
5	404	20%
6	147	7%
7 – Far-right	72	4%
Total	1962	
Missings	69	
Total sample	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

In the last general election, held in May 2025, you...

	Frequency	Percent
Went to vote and cast my vote	1548	76,2%
Went to vote but was unable to vote	37	1,8%
Did not go to vote	323	15,9%
Were underage / were unable to vote	54	2,7%
Missings	70	3,4%
Total sample	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

D4.2 - Social perception of scientific disinformation in Portugal

Region [Districts and NUTSII)

	Frequency	Percent
Aveiro	148	7,3%
Beja	18	0,9%
Braga	166	8,2%
Bragança	3	0,1%
Castelo Branco	34	1,7%
Coimbra	102	5,0%
Évora	38	1,9%
Faro	93	4,6%
Guarda	17	0,8%
Leiria	99	4,9%
Lisboa	480	23,6%
Portalegre	12	0,6%
Porto	392	19,3%
Santarém	94	4,6%
Setúbal	141	6,9%
Viana do Castelo	35	1,7%
Vila Real	17	0,8%
Viseu	46	2,3%
Açores	47	2,3%
Madeira	49	2,4%
Norte	760	37,4%
Centro	299	14,7%
Alentejo	162	8,0%
Algarve	93	4,6%
AM Lisboa	621	30,6%
Açores	47	2,3%
Madeira	49	2,4%
Total	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Job status

	Frequency	Percent
Working full time	1103	61,4%
Working part time	116	6,5%
Temporarily unemployed (i.e. between jobs)	55	3,1%
Retired	158	8,8%
Permanently disabled	17	1,0%
Taking care of home or family	32	1,8%
Student	112	6,2%
Unemployed	125	7,0%
Other	42	2,3%
Prefer not to say	36	2,0%
Total	1795	100,0%
System	236	11,6%
<i>Total</i>	<i>2031</i>	<i>100,0%</i>

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Job sector

	Frequency	Percent
Manufacturing	154	8,6%
Construction	73	4,1%
Retail	89	4,9%
Financial services	39	2,2%
Hospitality and leisure	73	4,0%
Accountancy	24	1,3%
Legal	38	2,1%
IT & telecoms	65	3,6%
Media/ marketing/ advertising/ PR & sales	21	1,2%
Medical & health services	105	5,8%
Education	116	6,5%
Transportation & distribution	69	3,8%
Real estate	13	0,7%
Other	332	18,5%
Don't know	65	3,6%
Not applicable – I am not currently employed	521	29,0%
Total	1795	100,0%
System	236	11,6%
<i>Total</i>	<i>2031</i>	<i>100.0</i>

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Devices

	Frequency	Percent
Has landline	1017	50,1%
Has smartphone	1977	97,3%
Uses smartphone	1932	95,1%
Total	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Do you feel that your activities are limited due to health problems?

	Frequency	Percent
Severely limited	78	3,8%
Limited, but not severely	535	26,3%
Not limited at all	1358	66,9%
Missing	60	3,0%
Total	2031	

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Are you a Portuguese national?

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	1983	97,6%
No	48	2,4%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

How long have you been living in Portugal?

	Percent	Valid Percent
5 anos ou mais	48	2,4%
System	1983	100%
Total	2031	100%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Population size of the place of residence

	Frequency	Percent
Less than 10.000 habitantes	578	28,4%
10.001 to 20.000 habitantes	403	19,8%
20.001 to 50.000 habitantes	304	14,9%
50.001 to 100.000 habitantes	266	13,1%
100.001 to 500.000 habitantes	282	13,9%
More than 500.000 habitantes	198	9,8%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Size of the household

	Frequency	Percent
1	248	13,8%
2	470	26,2%
3	495	27,6%
4	360	20,1%
5	109	6,1%
6	25	1,4%
7	16	0,9%
8 or more	10	0,5%
Prefer not to say	49	2,7%
Don't know	13	0,7%
Total	1795	100,0%
System	236	11,6%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Household members under 18

	Frequency	Percent
0	998	55,6%
1	427	23,8%
2	192	10,7%
3	48	2,7%
4	21	1,2%
5	16	0,9%
6 or more	4	0,2%
Prefer not to say	65	3,6%
Don't know	24	1,3%
Total	1795	100,0%
System	236	11,6%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

Household members under 18 for which the respondent is responsible for

	Frequency	Percent
0	514	28,7%
1	380	21,1%
2	171	9,5%
3	36	2,0%
4	10	0,6%
5 or more	4	0,2%
Don't know	36	2,0%
Prefer not to say	75	4,2%
There are no children below 18 in my household	570	31,7%
Total	1795	100,0%
System	236	11,6%
Total	2031	100,0%

Source: OberCom / IBERIFIER. Edition: OberCom. n=2031.

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IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It is made up of thirteen universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyze the Iberian digital media ecosystem and tackle the problem of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists and informants, young people and society as a whole.

For more information, look at the project website and its social media accounts:

Website: iberifier.eu

X: [@iberifier](https://twitter.com/iberifier)

Instagram: [@iberifier](https://www.instagram.com/iberifier)

LinkedIn: [IBERIFIER](https://www.linkedin.com/company/iberifier)

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